

Exploring the impact of Deep Learning in Masked Facial Recognition

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DEDICATION

This is dedicated to my parents for their endless efforts to help me accomplish my goals

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List of Symbols and Abbreviations

HOG	Histogram of Oriented Gradients
VGG	Visual Geometry Group
LBP	Local Binary Patterns
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
MTCNN	Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Neural Networks
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
MFR	Masked Facial Recognition
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
DDPM	Denosing Diffusion Probabilistic Model
DDIM	Denosing Diffusion Implicit Model
SVM	Support Vector Machines
MDMFR	Mask Detection Masked Face Recognition
RAM	Random Access Memory
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
DCGAN	Deep Convolutional Generative Adversarial Networks
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index
ViT	Vision Transformer
MAE	Masked Auto Encoder
MSE	Mean Square Error
IRM	Instance Relation Matching
IM	Instance Matching

GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
IAMGAN	Identity Aware Mask GAN
MFSR	Masked Face Segmentation and Recognition
CBAM	Convolutional Block Attention Module
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
MLP	Multi Layer Perceptron
SMFRD	Simulated Masked Face Recognition Dataset
FR	Face Recognition
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
CV	Computer Vision
NN	Neural Network
MHA	Multi-Headed Attention
FP32	Floating Point 32-bit
FP16	Floating Point 16-bit
SOTA	State Of The Art
KD	Knowledge Distillation
AKD	Adversarial Knowledge Distillation
SSH	Single Stage Headless Face Detector
PCN	Progressive Calibration Network
IoU	Intersection over Union
DCN	Deformable Convolutional Network
ϵ	A standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$
β_t	Noise scheduler at time stamp 't'
W_{in}	Width of the input image in a layer
H_{in}	Height of the input image in a layer
PCIe	Peripheral Component Interconnect Express

Abstract

Keywords: Masked Facial Recognition, Identity Verification, Multi-headed attention, Edge AI, Generative Models, Diffusion Models, Deep learning.

Since the advent of COVID-19 pandemic the problem of masked facial recognition has seen tremendous spike in both practice and academia. Existing state-of-the-art facial recognition models have struggled to accurately classify obscured faces, highlighting the pressing need for a comprehensive and resilient facial recognition framework. This demand stems from various practical applications, including surveillance, identity verification, ticket generation for parks, and attendance systems, necessitating a model that is both robust and efficient for real-time operation. This thesis addresses the need for such a solution by developing and validating a robust, time-efficient system tailored for real-time applications on Embedded AI hardware. In today's world, where mask-wearing has become ubiquitous for public health reasons, ensuring accurate and efficient facial recognition in such scenarios is paramount. Moreover, the practical applications of facial recognition extend beyond security and authentication to include personalized services and access control in various domains such as retail, banking, and healthcare.

Through comprehensive analysis, various architectural approaches have been thoroughly examined to address the challenges of masked facial recognition. An emphasis has been placed on employing a multi-headed attention mechanism, aimed at prioritizing unobscured facial regions. The choice of loss functions is to optimize the geodesic distance among embeddings of the masked faces. Careful consideration has been given to computational efficiency, ensuring the algorithm's suitability for real-time applications. Additionally, a diverse range of model scopes has been explored, including the utilization of minimal image features and employing generative models to unveil obscured faces. Following training, various optimization techniques are applied to enhance the system's performance on Edge AI devices, particularly leveraging the capabilities of platforms like the Jetson Xavier AGX.

Chapter 1

Introduction

With the continuous progression of technology, individuals increasingly rely on digital verification for establishing their identity. The integration of edge processing and IoT-based sensors has facilitated the adoption of biometric and speech recognition systems. Presently, the deployment of CCTV cameras for surveillance, activity monitoring sensors, and automated ticketing systems in public spaces has enabled the implementation of facial recognition and detection for streamlined processes. Facial recognition technology enhances security measures and proves particularly beneficial in scenarios where direct sensor contact is impractical or burdensome. A significant driving factor behind the adoption of automated recognition methods is the diminishing disparity between human capabilities and computer algorithms' proficiency in identifying individuals [1]. In the realm of Computer Vision applications, human performance serves as a benchmark for Bayer's optimal error, as alternative sources for classification tasks in image processing are scarce. This reduction in the disparity paves the way for the increased popularity of automated facial recognition systems.

Over the past few decades, numerous face recognition algorithms have been developed, ranging from heuristic approaches to advanced Deep Learning algorithms. These algorithms have been meticulously crafted with consideration for human facial structures. Among the conventional methods are Eigen Faces, Local Binary Patterns, Gabor wavelets, and HOG features. Despite the existence of advanced Deep Learning models such as VGGFace, FaceNet, and CNN-based architectures, they struggle significantly to produce reliable results across various scenarios, including pose variations, changes in lighting, and particularly with occluded faces [2]. This underscores the need for architectures that are resilient to the aforementioned variations in facial images while maintaining accuracy for both masked and unmasked faces. The primary issue arises from the obscured portion of the face due to masks, which covers almost half of the facial features and can be likened to corrupted pixels. Consequently, there arises a necessity for a model capable of identifying individuals by either reconstructing these pixels or utilizing available data. Traditional models were not crafted to address such

scenarios, resulting in poorer performance under evaluation [3]. Moreover, variations in lighting and pose present additional challenges, as real-time facial alignments may not precisely match with sensors. Hence, it is imperative to develop a resilient and effective pipeline for processing captured images and accurately identifying individuals therein.

Recognition of faces under occlusion can manifest in various ways. The occluding object may partially cover the face, with scenarios ranging from it obscuring approximately 70 percent of the face to merely concealing the lips. It is essential to acknowledge that the effectiveness of a robust face recognition model hinges greatly on its ability to handle both occluded and unoccluded facial regions. The provided image illustrates diverse occlusion scenarios, encompassing examples within and across classes [4].

Figure 1.1: A demonstration of various occlusion scenarios

It's evident that masked face recognition introduces diverse occlusion scenarios, encompassing variations such as individuals wearing different masks or similar ones, along with other forms of occlusion. While robust algorithms are essential across various applications like online attendance, park ticketing, and mobile phone unlocking, the need for background noise resilience is particularly emphasized in surveillance contexts. Ensuring precise localization of captured facial data is crucial in these scenarios. Furthermore, neglecting to adjust for occluded facial regions could significantly impede the algorithm's ability to distinguish between different classes wearing the same mask.

Later, a detailed discussion will explore how the management of obscured facial areas can profoundly affect algorithmic accuracy. This aspect stands as the algorithm's pivotal and contentious component, akin in significance to frequently adjusted hyperparameters in a Neural Network. The method chosen for recognizing faces with coverings also depends on how the model will be used. Sometimes, getting the timing just right

might require a different approach to covered areas than when focusing solely on accuracy. However, it's still important to examine and possibly test different methods for how the algorithm deals with both covered and uncovered parts of the face. This will form the basis of the analysis of the previously presented algorithms extending to our own proposed models and approaches to solve the problem.

1.1 Problem Definition

Much of the work have been carried out on facial recognition before the outbreak of COVID-19. In most cases the focus was to ensure facial recognition with a clear face image which later transformed into a pose estimation problem under various scenarios including lighting changes, side facial view and blurred images. The main problem in this case was the discrepancy among the training data distribution and the test data. Many benchmark datasets have been published in this regard to ensure an exhaustive and a diverse representation of the facial images. Furthermore, techniques such as Data Augmentation and some other standard computer vision operations help to ensure the same data distribution for the training and the test dataset. Following this approach for data preprocessing and using the appropriate architecture, researchers have developed many robust facial recognition systems. They tend to perform well on possible pose estimation and lighting changes to the extent that they exceed the human level performance, which serves as a proxy for Bayesian error. Few of the renowned state-of-the-art models for unobscured facial recognition are FaceNet, Deep Face, DeepID, InsightFace, and MTCNN [5,6,7,8,9]. An additional contribution made in some of these models is their robustness towards the possible adversarial attack commonly known as "Face Spoofing". It helps in ensuring that the model is not fooled by an image of the face rather than the actual face itself. It is common particularly in sensitive matters such as surveillance and attendance systems where the chances of individuals trying to cheat the system are significantly higher.

Although these Deep Learning models were remarkably exceptional in recognizing visible faces, they tend to struggle when they have been validated on the masked faces. This particular domain gained increased attention following the COVID-19 pandemic, and its utility can be expanded to include surveillance purposes, as well as in regions where certain female individuals are culturally mandated to wear a hijab. Expanding on this idea a model used in such applications needs to be further optimized both in terms of the architecture and the timing constraints for any good use. The work carried out in this thesis is regarding the timing optimization of the masked facial recognition while ensuring robustness in terms of the accuracy and the confidence of the model in both masked and unmasked cases. It can be considered as an elevation of the previously trained face recognition models but with a much wider scope of applications. To validate the best possible architecture's performance for a real-time

application, our model has been deployed on the CUDA cores of an AI accelerated embedded hardware that is Jetson Xavier AGX [10]. It features CUDA and Tensor cores that allow embarrassingly parallel tasks such as a typical Neural Network to execute much more efficiently compared to a standard CPU operation. Moreover, the device itself is compact and robust enough to be considered for deployment in remote areas as an independent node or perhaps an integral part of a bigger IoT network.

1.2 Motivation

The problem of face recognition has been researched in the past decade to the extent that it was thought to be completely solved. Many state of the art algorithms for face recognition and recognition have been developed with a focus on pose estimation and changes in the background including external lighting effects. The performance of state-of-the-art face recognition model such as VGGFace dropped when tested on the masked dataset by 40% that is from 82.1% on unmasked faces to 40.4% on masked dataset [4]. The same trend of decline is seen with respect to other models including FaceNet, DeepFace and DeepID. The motivation for this research can therefore be summarized as follows.

- To improve the conventional facial recognition models in order to be able to adapt not only the varying pose estimation scenarios but also to cater occlusion.
- The shallow masked facial recognition models such as the one cited in [11] that employs AlexNet as the backbone with the SVM classifier comes with the drawback that they are designed for closed class classification problems. These models tend to perform well in scenarios including attendance systems when there are fixed number of students or in the security related problems with access to limited number of individuals. The problem of open-class classification was not addressed which plays a crucial role in applications such as surveillance and automated ticketing systems.
- MFR finds its application in the problems that requires real-time operation. No paper or research material was found to the best of our knowledge that had utilized any model post-processing techniques or optimizations to be able to deploy the model on the hardware. No or negligible discussions have been found in the papers with attention regarding the timing efficiency of the model. This can potentially be a serious bottleneck when trying to use such models in practice.
- Some of the recently developed MFR papers have utilized generative models such as Auto encoders in [12] and custom made GAN in [13]. These models tend to approach the problem by treating the masked portion of the face as corrupted

pixels and therefore they reconstruct the face semantically to assume "no noise" facial image. One of the problems with these models is their time consumption and too much resource allocation is required to restore the image which is often not suited for real-time operation and certainly not to be able to deploy on a node where computational resources are also limited.

- Another ethical aspect to take into consideration are those areas where it is forbidden to wear hijab for Muslim women as it hinders in their identity recognition. This problem can be solved if only for once their face can be recorded in the database and later they can be verified at security checkpoints without having to reveal their masks.

1.3 Proposed Solution

To solve the problems briefly highlighted in the previous sections, we have reviewed both the generative models and the attention-based mechanisms. In the case of Generative models, we have used the novel approach of utilizing Diffusion Models. Unlike GANs, the image generation process is tractable, which paves the way for semantically correlated images. It is an absolute necessity for the masked facial recognition problem as the generated images are required not only to be accurate but also related to the facial features of the same person. Among the diffusion models themselves, more emphasis has been given to the DDIM than to their probabilistic counterparts. DDIM offers a better sampler, and we can always sample the image for different sampling paths with having the same Markov chain for the forward diffusion process. This is because, unlike DDPM, the focus of the DDIM is more on the denoising part of the image rather than actually modeling the probability distribution of the masked faces. On the other hand, the attention-based mechanism approach ensures better performance of our model by adaptively paying attention to the hidden and unoccluded parts of the face. The idea is similar to the optimization techniques used in famous optimizer such as RMSProp, Adam and some commonly known algorithms including L1 and L2 regularization. Focusing more on the visible facial areas while still acknowledging the obscured parts is crucial to retain information from the corrupted pixels in prior methods, without assimilating unnecessary patterns from the masked regions of the face.

The algorithms are then validated on the mentioned Embedded AI accelerator board for the real-time computational complexity and the time consumption. The results are compiled and presented in this thesis as we move along. The chosen architecture is suited for real-time applications and is comparable with the known state-of-the-art algorithms in terms of accuracy and the time efficiency. A blue print of the model architecture has been shown below.

Figure 1.2: Outline of the proposed model architecture

The proposed architecture works in stages to extract independent features for better performance. The first stage is the face verification process, which extracts the facial coordinates from external background noise. The mask detection stage follows it, a semantic segmentation for the face mask. The last stage is face recognition, which can be achieved by the DDIM or the attention-based mechanisms depending on the trigger signal. This signal is externally supplied at the time of inference depending upon the device to which it is subjected to operate. The analysis and the results for the best possible architecture based on the trade-off for accuracy and computational resources have been shared in the later parts of this thesis.

1.4 Research Methodology

The adopted research methodologies aim to follow objectives:

- To explore and research extensively on state-of-the-art facial and masked facial recognition model architectures.
- In-depth analysis of the pros and cons of the architectures with respect to both the accuracy and the time efficiency.

- Exploring the Architecture of Jetson Xavier AGX for Streamlined Model Deployment Post-Training.
- To develop a masked facial recognition pipeline that seamlessly identifies faces regardless of masks or background noise, rivaling the robustness of state-of-the-art models. Furthermore, our focus lies on optimizing inference time to ensure swift real-time deployment.
- Exploring the model optimization technique including model pruning, quantization, knowledge distillation, sparse and dynamic inference for better timing efficiency while maintaining the drop in accuracy within bounds
- Deployment and validation of the MFR model on the hardware, post-optimization. The utilization of the CUDA and Tensor Cores needs to be optimized for the eloquent number of threads, blocks and proper allocation of the grids inside the GPU.

1.5 Thesis Organization

The thesis in the coming chapters has been organized as follows:

- In Chapter 02, all the available literature on the facial and masked facial recognition architectures has been compiled with a special focus on the time of inference and the accuracy of the model on state-of-the-art datasets.
- Chapter 03 is dedicated to the extensive analysis and details of the implementation with and without the hardware. In this section, a comprehensive discussion has been carried out on the best possible architecture and the potential tradeoffs between accuracy and the efficient time of inference for real-time application. It includes all the details of the proposed pipeline, from the cleaning of the dataset to the model post-processing and deployment on the hardware.
- Chapter 04 is dedicated to the discussion regarding the obtained results.
- Chapter 05 serves as both the conclusion, summarizing the findings and implications of the study, and as a platform for outlining future research directions and potential advancements in the field.

Chapter 2

Background Study

In computer vision, recognizing faces is a standout application. It works like our natural ability to tell people apart by their faces. Unlike natural language processing and time series forecasting, computer vision is an area where the accuracy of a model can often be fine-tuned to the point where it's highly reliable for making decisions. It is usually because of the strong ability of humans to be good at image recognition. Therefore, it acts as the Bayes' Optimal error and guides us nicely as to what factors can lead to better model output. It's crucial to determine the optimal error for a specific problem. Without this estimate, it becomes challenging to assess whether we're encountering issues like overfitting, underfitting, or a mismatch in probability distribution between the training and test datasets. Moving forward this information will be super helpful in optimizing our proposed model architecture for the benchmark datasets. The human level performance that can potentially serves as the Bayes' optimal error is the recognition accuracy of an expert in the field [14]. For instance, in the case of masked facial recognition, humans tend to perform well to recognize faces that are partially occluded. It is worthwhile to note that for a human to recognize a person, it might also take into account other factors such as Gait analysis, speech recognition and psychological behavior. The ceiling on the optimal error should therefore be less than the average human recognition for a person. A good reference for the performance optimization is to compare the newly trained model with the previously known state-of-the-art models.

The pursuit to automate facial recognition is not a new one. Many researchers have published their work in the past few decades even before the formal advent of Deep Learning and Neural Networks in practice. The improvements have been made in the early days to the algorithms so much that many of the recent algorithms utilize a hybrid model having both the Neural Networks followed by the classical algorithms for classification. In the coming section a detailed discussion will be carried out on the previously design architectures including their pros and cons. This extensive review of the literature on facial recognition will shape our approach of designing our own

algorithm that is both robust and efficient in terms of the inference time.

2.1 Facial Recognition vs Masked Facial recognition

It is important to note the difference before analyzing the architectures for masked facial recognition. Before COVID-19, identity recognition primarily centered around facial recognition, requiring a clear, unobstructed view of the entire face. In MFR however, almost half of the face is hidden behind some object that can be a face mask, scarf, hat, or synthetic image inpainting. The differences can therefore be summarized as under.

- Facial recognition with the face being fully visible is much easier as the architecture can be designed to extract features from the raw image followed by the classifier algorithm. It can be projected as the multi-class classification problem with the typical CNN + fully connected layers architecture. Other classifiers such as SVM or tree based classification schemes may as well be utilized depending upon the dataset.
- The image below demonstrates the masked and the unmasked image of the same individual, in this case taken from CelebA dataset [15].

Figure 2.1: Masked version of the data sample from CelebA dataset

The masked version of the image has been created utilizing the dlib based features for capturing the necessary features and the face tilt. The implementation is carried out with the help of an API known as "MaskTheFace" [16]. The highlighted mask represents the set of corrupted pixels that alters the overall data distribution, leading to a decrease in the model's accuracy. The performance of the trained model on unmasked faces will therefore be sub optimal on masked faces due to the change in the data distribution of the training and the test data.

- Apart from using the same model, there is a limitation of using the same architecture on masked face dataset. This is because once the face has been cropped out of the background noise, the image is only the relevant features. Therefore, the recognition could have been done easily by utilizing the embedding-based models for the open-end classification problem and CNN for the closed-end ones. In MFR the corrupted pixels either needs to be ignored, restored, or given lower weights by employing the attention-based mechanisms.
- MFR might also pose an additional challenge due to the lack of the vast dataset compared to the unmasked faces. Although, the masked faces can be generated synthetically the distribution of the synthetic masked faces might differ significantly in comparison to the actual face masks.

Based on the arguments stated above, MFR will be dealt with entirely differently from normal facial recognition, and it also states why the conventional facial recognition models underperform when tested on the masked dataset. The algorithms discussed in this case will mostly be for masked facial recognition, with any exceptions in the case of an idea borrowed from the facial recognition counterpart.

2.2 Survey of Architectures and Algorithms

This section will explore the algorithms and architectures that have been documented for facial recognition in masked scenarios. Particular focus and attention will be given to the timing efficiency of the algorithms if documented. Their advantages and disadvantages will also be examined in challenging scenarios, such as pose variations, lighting conditions changes, and background noise. For ease of analysis, all the literature on this particular topic can be divided based on how they treat the corrupted pixels occluded by the face mask. Based on this, we can have three(3) different types of architectures, stated below:

- Ignores the face mask and uses it as a helpful feature as in the case of visible faces.

- Restores the occluded faces by utilizing generative models.
- Attention-based approaches partially utilize masked pixels and focus only on the visible part of the face.

All three (3) approaches will be discussed subsequently, stating their pros and cons, which will form the basis of our improved architecture.

2.3 Face Mask utilization approach

The common theme in these architectures is the utilization of face mask as the normal facial pixel to extract features from the raw image. The main difference in all these architectures is the use of feature extraction layers and their classifiers for closed-end classification problem. Some of the eminent algorithms have been discussed as under.

2.3.1 Disguised Face Recognition using AlexNet + SVM

One of the common approaches for feature extraction is the use of transfer learning. The backbone model used in [11] was AlexNet that have been trained on the ImageNet dataset for a closed classification problem, having a total of 1000 different objects [17]. The architecture can be summarized as shown in the image below [11].

Figure 2.2: MFR pipeline with robustness to background noise

The pipeline suggested in the research provides a mechanism of removing the background noise by employing a face detection algorithm based on haar-cascade classifier. After cropping the face, the image is processed as a set of raw features devoid of noise, which are then extracted using AlexNet. Specifically, only the convolutional layers of AlexNet are employed for feature extraction, omitting the softmax layer due to discrepancies in the number of facial entities between the dataset used and the ImageNet dataset for training AlexNet. Following the extraction of embeddings by the AlexNet model, a multiclass SVM classifier is employed.

AlexNet can be act as an effective tool for feature extraction from raw images. The architecture for for the backbone model used in this pipeline is a combination of the convolutional layers, maxpooling and the dropout layer. The detailed architecture for the model has been tabulated below.

Table 2.1. Description of the AlexNet architecture [18]

Layer	# Filters/ Neurons	Filter Size	Stride	Pad	Size of Feature Map	Activation Function
Input	-	$227 \times 227 \times 3$				
Conv 1	96	11×11	4	Same	$55 \times 55 \times 96$	ReLU
Pool 1		3×3	2		$27 \times 27 \times 96$	
Conv 2	256	5×5	1	Same	$27 \times 27 \times 256$	ReLU
Pool 2		3×3	2		$13 \times 13 \times 256$	
Conv 3	384	3×3	1	Same	$13 \times 13 \times 384$	ReLU
Conv 4	384	3×3	1	Same	$13 \times 13 \times 384$	ReLU
Conv 5	256	3×3	1	Same	$13 \times 13 \times 256$	ReLU
Pool 3		3×3	2		$6 \times 6 \times 256$	
Dropout 1	rate = 0.5				$6 \times 6 \times 256$	

While the neural network architecture may appear simplistic, its effectiveness is bolstered by the extensive training performed on the expansive ImageNet dataset. As a result, the model is adept at extracting sturdy features from images. Another important aspect of using the AlexNet is the extensive number of filters used in a layer. Overall, it has around 62.3 Million learnable parameters. Last but not the least, SVM was used for classification which can help in both the linear and non-linear classification problem.

2.3.1.1 Limitations of the architecture

The limitations in the discussed pipeline are stated below.

- The pipeline was initially crafted specifically for the closed-case classification issue. To accurately classify the identity of a new individual, rigorous retraining

is required because architectural adjustments are necessary. This is due to the incorporation of a softmax activation function in the final layer, alongside a set number of neurons.

- The dataset used in this paper was not a custom made dataset and the model was not validated on any benchmark dataset. The dataset contained a total of 180 images belonging to three (3) different individuals. This dataset is too thin and a much higher accuracy can be achieved with simpler architectures.
- The dataset contained images of people from the same ethnicity, belonging to the same age group. The problem with this approach is that even if the model has achieved close to 100% accuracy, it might as well under perform when tested on the real-time dataset as the data distribution of the training and test dataset will differ significantly. This problem is very well-known in the field of Machine Learning and is commonly referred as "Data Drift" [19].
- The haar-cascade facial detector does not work very well when exposed to multiple faces in an image, and therefore the robustness of the model to the background noise cannot effectively translate into recognizing multiple person in a single frame.

2.3.2 DeepMaskNet for Masked Facial recognition

A DeepMasknet model has also been developed to utilize the occlusion as part of the facial features [2]. It deals with the face mask as if those were the pixels of the face itself. The pipeline proposed in this case was novel and independent of any backbone model with an additional feature of detecting the face mask itself. The key difference of the DeepMaskNet model from its counterpart is the detection of the face mask at the end of the model architecture. This recognition of face mask presence proves valuable in situations where adherence to mask-wearing regulations is deemed as imperative as a duty. An advantage of their proposed architecture is the sharing of the feature embedding by both the face recognition and the face mask detection resulting in an efficient implementation in terms of the model's inference time. The implemented model also incorporated Batch Normalization Layers, enabling each layer to autonomously learn features by ensuring that both input and output activation share the same mean and variance of the data mapping. The implementation of the forward pass of a Neural Network can be mathematically expressed as follows.

$$Z^{[l]} = W^{[l]} \cdot A^{[l-1]} + b^{[l]}$$

where $W^{[l]}$ represents the weights of the l th layer, having dimensions $(n^{[l]} \times n^{[l-1]})$. $b^{[l]}$ denotes the bias of the l th layer, with dimensions $(n^{[l]} \times m)$, where m stands for

the batch size of the image dataset. $A^{[l-1]}$ stands for the activations from the previous layer, possessing dimensions $(n^{[l-1]} \times m)$. Here, $n^{[l]}$ and $n^{[l-1]}$ indicate the number of neurons in the l th and $(l - 1)$ th layers, respectively.

For the case of Batch Normalization layers, the activation are normalized and mapped onto the fixed mean and the variance.

$$Z_{\text{norm}}^{[l]} = \frac{Z^{[l]} - \mu}{\sigma}$$

Finally, the fixed mean and the variance of the activation for a given layer is established.

$$Z^{\sim} = \gamma^{[l]} + \beta^{[l]} \cdot Z_{\text{norm}}^{[l]}$$

$$A^{[l]} = \text{ReLU}(Z^{\sim})$$

With this additional Batch Normalization layer the training of the model was carried out much more efficiently. The pipeline utilized fully connected layers for the classification rather than classical algorithms such as SVM, or tree based classification. The detailed architecture is as shown below.

Figure 2.3: Architecture of the DeepMaskNet model

The main advantage of this methodology is the lack of any backbone models which allow for the faster execution of the model at inference time.

2.3.2.1 MDMFR Dataset

The paper also proposed a dataset known as the Mask Detection Masked Face Recognition dataset. The proposed model architecture was trained on the same dataset. It contains the training, validation and the test dataset with segmentation of the images into masked and unmasked labels. The dataset comprises 6005 images, with 5548 featuring males and 457 featuring females. The images encompass various types of masks including surgical, cloth, N95, and KN95, all presented in RGB format with three channels. Further specifics of the dataset are provided in the table below.

Table 2.2. Gender based classification for MDMFR

Samples	Gender	
	Male	Female
With Mask	2923	251
Without Mask	2625	206
Total	5548	457

Variations of masks were utilized in collecting the dataset, with the number of images corresponding to each type of mask listed below.

Table 2.3. Classification of the masked images in MDMFR

Samples	Count
Surgical Masks	2892
Cloth Masks	121
N95 and KN95 Masks	164

The model has achieved remarkable performance on the mentioned dataset with a training time of 192 minutes and 4 seconds on an Intel i5-5200U process with an 8GB RAM. The model has been trained for a total of 14 epochs with 42 iterations per epoch. The dataset was shuffled on each epoch with the validation frequency of 30, accompanied by the learning rate of 0.01. The model was evaluated on parameters other than accuracy. The results for Precision, Recall, and the F1-score reported for the model was as good as the masked face recognition accuracy.

2.3.2.2 Limitations of the architecture

Below are the limitations of the proposed pipeline for DeepMaskNet.

- The dataset used to train the DeepMaskNet model was not diverse and it was limited in the probability distribution. The dataset mostly contained images of the adults with Asian ethnicity. It means that even though the model performed exceptionally well on the partitioned training and the test dataset, it may not perform equally well when deployed in production.
- The inference time of the model was not evaluated in real-time, and the training time was recorded for a very limited dataset. Hence, the model cannot be conclusively regarded as time efficient.
- The pipeline did not feature any immunity to the background noise. The face in an image cannot be cropped in the presence of objects other than the human face itself. The algorithm will work efficiently if and only if it had the face of a person capturing the entire frame of the image.
- The algorithm has not shown any signs of multiple face recognition capability. The architecture is strictly classifying each image as a single person due to the softmax activation function used at the output layer with the neurons equal to the total number of classes in the dataset.

2.3.3 PCA based Masked Facial Recognition

Principal Component Analysis is one of the statistical measures for extracting features based on the quantities, such as the mean and variance of the dataset. In [20], the authors propose a novel approach that utilizes a fast and time-efficient pipeline for implementation. The algorithm mainly consists of the face cropping step to remove background noise, followed by the feature extraction stage. The extracted weights are then compared to the threshold, and if we exceed that, the face is recognized; otherwise, it is not. The training part of the feature extraction stage is based on the following steps:

- Extract the input data from the dataset in the form of a batch
- Calculate the mean of the data, and subtract it from the actual image
- Compute the Covariance matrix
- Compute the Eigen vector and Eigen values
- Find the greatest Eigen value

- Compute the weights

The detailed architecture for the model is as shown below [20].

Figure 2.4: PCA based Masked Facial Recognition Model

The face extraction stage is implemented by the Viola-Jones detector, followed by the feature extraction stage initiated by the PCA. The main advantage and concept

of using PCA is that it works well for dimensionality reduction, which is a bonus for the inference time efficiency of the model. The model's accuracy will be maximum for the correlated data, as is the case for images of people with the same ethnicity. The computations for the Component analysis are simple and can be parallelized on the CUDA cores when implemented on hardware such as Jetson Xavier.

2.3.3.1 Limitations of the architecture

In this architecture there were the following limitations:

- The dataset chosen for the training of the model was collected locally and the trained model was not validation on any of the benchmark datasets. The dataset lacked facial diversity and contained faces of the people from the same ethnicity, therefore the model was not evaluated potentially to the maximum.
- The utilization of PCA for the feature extraction instead of a dedicated CNN allows for faster execution time. However, with this architecture the model assumes predominantly that the images presented for inference are correlated much like of the people belonging to the same region.
- PCA is generally not preferred for the learning complex data distributions are the components in this algorithm are mostly linearly related. Images, particularly the faces are samples of the complex dataset. It is highly possible that the model will tend to under perform when presented with the real-time test dataset.
- The learnable parameters for the PCA are far too less to map complex features into a feature embedding that can eventually be used for accurate classification. A neural network inspired by the encoder of the Auto encoders or Vision Transformers might have been a better choice.
- The major drawback of the Viola-Jones detector, used for the facial extraction in this pipeline is its limitation to successfully detect facial images in case of occlusion. MFR performance of a model will be seriously compromised with the utilization of this detector in the pipeline.
- Last but not the least, the main drawback of the Viola-Jones detector is the high percentage of the false positives and lack of robustness to the illumination and pose estimation. It emphasizes the fact that the face cannot be extracted properly from the background until and unless majority of the pixels belong to the clear facial image without any illumination or pose variations. The robustness of the algorithm is in serious jeopardy due to the stated bottleneck.

2.4 Face restoration approach for MFR via Generative Models

It has been seen in the previous category of approaches that the face mask was considered an essential part of the face itself. Therefore, the feature extraction layers were utilized on the entire occluded region. It is a significant assumption in Masked Facial Recognition since the mask or the occlusion holds no information for the person wearing it. A model that is robust to the external noise and performs significantly well on the diverse dataset remains a challenge face mask utilization approach. An alternative to the MFR is the use of generative models to restore a person's facial pixels. It relies on the fact that the unoccluded faces have been recognized sometimes better than the human-level performance [21,22]. Therefore, if the face can be adequately restored, we will have the face recognized, closing the gap between the accuracy of the model and Bayes' Optimal error [23,24,25]. Generative models, since the advent of GAN, have been the centre of attraction for generating images from noise based on the prompt. In MFR, these models can be utilized to restore the occluded portion of the face. The daunting challenge in these architectures is to ensure that the generated face of the individual is semantically related to the original person. Furthermore, the choice of the generative model contributes significantly to the robustness of the MFR pipeline. From GANs to diffusion models, MFR has explored numerous possibilities, with some still requiring refinement and further exploration for improvement. All of the notables literature have been presented in this section with inspiration into our own proposed model.

2.4.1 GAN based Face Reconstruction for Masked-Face

One of the foremost choices among generative models is Generative Adversarial Networks, first presented by Ian Goodfellow et al. in 2014 [26]. The architecture of these models is based on the zero-sum game that relies on two independent neural networks, commonly referred to as the Generator and the Discriminator. The Generator is responsible for generating images from isotropic Gaussian noise, while the Discriminator acts as a binary classifier, distinguishing between the generated images labeled as either 'Real' or 'Fake'. The adversarial training of GAN allows the generation of images from essentially nothing. In [27], a novel approach for masked face recognition has been presented, utilizing GAN for reconstructing the face followed by state-of-the-art models for non-occluded facial recognition. There have been many variants of the standard GAN model, one of such variants used in this paper is commonly known as "CycleGAN". CycleGAN is most commonly known for the Image-to-Image translation task, such as in this case where the masked face is being tried to transform into the non-occluded face. In this case, the architecture consists of 2 generators and a discriminator for

each. For the sake of clarity the architecture of CycleGAN and its working have been explained below.

2.4.1.1 CycleGAN architecture for MFR

The fundamental backbone of this approach was the use of CycleGAN for Image-to-Image translation particularly used to transform masked image into the non-occluded face images. Unlike the standard GAN, CycleGAN utilizes a pair of generators and a discriminator against each. The architecture of has been shown below.

Figure 2.5: CycleGAN architecture for Face restoration

The role of Generators within GANs can be validated by their effort to mimic the distribution of data transitioning between masked and unmasked states, and vice versa. This data distribution is exemplified as $a \sim p_{data}(a)$, and $b \sim p_{data}(b)$, where the generator endeavors to map the provided input image. Simultaneously, the discriminator assesses each generated image to categorize it as "Real" or "Fake". In the case of masked face recognition, though, there must be a few considerations regarding the overall architecture, as stated below.

- In the original paper [27], the authors utilized a dlib-based feature extractor to map the mask onto the dedicated regions of the face using MaskTheFace API [16]. This is crucial in ensuring that we have a reliable means of replicating the data distribution of the masked faces given a non-occluded image. It serves as the ground truth for the Discriminator that is evaluating the Generator responsible for learning the masked face data distribution.
- The primary objective of the GAN upon its inception was to generate images capable of deceiving the discriminator into perceiving them as authentic. However,

in this particular context, the image not only needs to be genuine but also needs to maintain semantic relevance to the individual it represents. This necessitates establishing correlation between the visible portion of the face and the masked area. Consequently, this influences the selection of the loss function

Based on the arguments the CycleGAN used in the paper included each generator with the inclusion of the cycle consistency loss function along with the adversarial loss of the generators. The adversarial loss function of the generator is responsible for generating real images. The loss function used in the paper is the conventional Minimax loss function stated by the following equation

$$\lambda_{\text{GAN}}(G, D_B, A, B) = \mathbb{E}_{b \sim p_{data}(b)}[\log D_B(b)] + \mathbb{E}_{a \sim p_{data}(a)}[\log(1 - D_B(G(a)))] \quad (2.1)$$

where:

- $G(a)$ operates on the data distribution A to generate B .
- D_B is the discriminator operating on both the generated images $G(a)$ and the original images A .

The Generator aims to minimize the stated loss function while the Discriminator tries to maximize it. The adversarial training is continued unless the Discriminator’s classification accuracy is 50% which is as good as a coin toss. To ensure the semantic correlation among the reconstructed face with the intended person, the cycle consistency loss has been stated below.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{cyc}}(G, F) = \mathbb{E}_{a \sim p_{data}(a)}[\|F(G(a)) - a\|_1] + \mathbb{E}_{b \sim p_{data}(b)}[\|G(F(b)) - b\|_1] \quad (2.2)$$

The stated loss function is the L1-norm distance between the generated image distribution and the ground truth. The actual loss function used in the paper is in fact the sum equation (2.1) and (2.2), stated as follows.

$$\mathcal{L} = \lambda_{\text{GAN}}(G, D_B, A, B) + \mathcal{L}\lambda_{\text{GAN}}(F, D_A, B, A) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{cyc}}(G, F) \quad (2.3)$$

The architecture for the GAN used in the paper is Deep Convolution Generative Adversarial Nets with the initial convolutional layers followed by the 64-channel convolutional ResNET block. The Discriminator used for the pipeline included 70x70 patch GAN to evaluate the performance on the subgrid of the image rather than the entire image itself or on the pixel level. It is important to note that this approach is similar to the batch processing of the dataset in a Machine Learning model, where it is used to accelerate the training of the network. Furthermore, just like the case of Batch Gradient Descent, it also helps in the backpropagation of the algorithm by removing the noise of updating the weights after each iteration.

2.4.1.2 Dataset and Evaluation Metric

The paper employs a custom dataset comprising 8131 unpaired facial images, each with a resolution of 256x256 pixels. This dataset includes both masked and unmasked samples, and the model undergoes training for a total of 150 epochs. The lambda value utilized is set to 10. Additionally, a distinct dataset containing 2118 masked faces is utilized for model evaluation. Consistent with the methodology outlined in the original CycleGAN paper [29], both perceptual and quantitative measures are employed to assess image quality.

For the quantitative measure part, the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) has been utilized. This metric compares images based on their luminance, contrast, and structural information. Luminance represents the mean intensity of the images, while contrast corresponds to their standard deviation. Structural similarity quantifies the correlation between the structures present in the images.

The SSIM index is computed using the following equations:

$$L(x, y) = \frac{2 \cdot \mu_x \cdot \mu_y + C_1}{\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1} \quad (2.4)$$

$$C(x, y) = \frac{2 \cdot \sigma_x \cdot \sigma_y + C_2}{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2} \quad (2.5)$$

$$S(x, y) = \frac{\sigma_{xy} + C_3}{\sigma_x \cdot \sigma_y + C_3} \quad (2.6)$$

$$SSIM(x, y) = L(x, y) \cdot C(x, y) \cdot S(x, y) \quad (2.7)$$

2.4.1.3 Limitations of the architecture

The limitations of the architecture have been shared as follows.

- The architecture introduced a method for image-to-image translation with masked images; however, it lacked evaluation of the complete pipeline, specifically using a state-of-the-art face recognition model to verify recognition accuracy.
- Generative models are known for their time-consuming nature, raising concerns about real-time deployment. The paper’s omission of any reference to time efficiency validation leaves implementation for real-time applications questionable.
- While the paper emphasized perceptual evaluation of generated images, better perceptual accuracy does not necessarily guarantee efficient performance with face recognition models, as recognition of individuals may vary.

- The image generation process remains opaque, with the model essentially operating as a black box. Despite its awareness of the masking process, its ability to unmask images equally well is assumed.
- Adversarial training is inherently unstable, with GANs prone to issues like Mode Collapse [30], where the Generator outputs images with minor variations, failing to capture the full diversity of the data distribution. Additionally, as the Generator improves, its output becomes less informative as classification accuracy approaches 50%.

2.4.2 Privacy Preserving Face Recognition using Masked Autoencoders

Autoencoders indeed represent another class of generative models that have been widely employed in image-to-image translation [31]. Their versatility extends across various domains, encompassing tasks such as image denoising, synthesis, color enhancement, and beyond. They are commonly used to learn the data distribution of a given dataset using an Encoder-Decoder architecture. The encoder functions to map the input image onto a latent space with reduced dimensionality. Subsequently, a straightforward decoder employing an upsampling architecture reconstructs the original image. A loss function is applied to ensure the fidelity of the generated image to the input. A modified approach in [32] uses Masked Autoencoders for masked face recognition. The primary task for deploying generative models is the same as before. It is used to generate unmasked facial images using masked ones. An additional layer of feature in this paper is the preservation of privacy as the model can generate the image of a person that may reveal his/her identity causing a huge problem. The Masked auto encoders utilize an encoder of the conventional ViT [33] that utilizes the image tokens extracted from the non-overlapping 2D grids of the image. The idea of the encoder is to take in the masked patches of the image with their corresponding positional embedding. The masked patches of the image are ruled out of the encoder's input to ensure over growing length of the encoder itself. This is essential to ensure that the Encoder is more deep rather than in length for better learning of the features and dimensionality reduction. On the decoder side of the architecture the masked patches are then reused with their unique embedding to ensure the images are put back together and that the reconstruction is reliable. The trained model in the paper is termed as FaceMAE with the detailed architecture shown as follows [32].

Figure 2.6: FaceMAE architecture for masked face reconstruction

The pipeline has been shown for both the training and deployment stages. The individual blocks utilized mainly feature MAE, which has been trained on the masked image, in this case, the masked facial photos. The reconstructed image is then compared with the original one to ensure image fidelity. One of the most common choices for the loss function is Mean Square Error to compare the patches or the pixels themselves. However, it fails to meet the semantically comparing data distribution requirement. To solve this issue, the architecture uses a separate model to generate the embedding of the original and the reconstructed images and then compare them using Euclidean distance. This method has been called Instance Relation Matching (IRM) in the paper. This is mentioned by the pre-trained backbone model in the architecture shown above. Last but not least, the model in the deployment stage uses a different dataset with the same trained MAE without the pre-trained backbone. As explained earlier, the idea behind the generative models in MFR is to utilize state-of-the-art face recognition models by ensuring the reliable generation of the image. The same idea has been used in the deployment stage, including the ArcFace loss function that tries to maximize the geodesic distance among the feature embedding [34]. The details of the pre-trained backbone model in the training stage of the model is ResNet50. Still, they can be achieved either with the feature extraction layer of the models such as ResNet, FaceNet or MobileNet [35,36,37]. One of the added advantages of utilizing MAE is that it is a self-supervised algorithm and does not have extra labels for the training, which ensures the flexibility of the datasets that can be used.

2.4.2.1 Datasets

The datasets used for the training are WebFace260M and CASIA-Webface [38,39]. The prior dataset contains a total of 260 Million images, and only 10% of the images have been used for the training of FaceMAE in the stated pipeline.

2.4.2.2 Limitations of the architecture

The limitations of the pipeline presented in the paper are as follows.

- The paper discussed the use of masked faces for face reconstruction. Still, the dataset utilized for the training consisted of visible faces, and the masking of the face was completely based on losing some of the positional embedding patches.
- The utilization of the lost patches from an image can be thought of as an image-impainting problem. The model was neither tested on the real masks on an image nor considered any synthetic masking of the training dataset with visible faces.
- There is no consideration to the background noise removal. In the case of deploying the model for surveillance systems, the captured image often contains the image with only a single patch containing the face itself. The currently proposed architecture would include a single positional embedding and might be ignored, or even if considered, it will be considered as a single element.
- The comparison in the results portion have not been made with the state-of-the-art MFR models to compare the accuracy and overall latency in a real-time network.
- The model information in terms of the hardware have been present such as the utilization of the modern A100 GPU but the inference time of the model have neither been reported nor discussed to reduce.

2.4.3 Masked Face Recognition with Generative Data Augmentation

Another approach within generative models involves generating datasets using data augmentation techniques [40]. This approach presents a scenario for image-to-image translation that can produce masked faces from visible face datasets, thereby expanding the available dataset. This is achieved by employing the CycleGAN architecture with multiple Generators and Discriminators, as proposed in the paper and termed IAMGAN, to preserve identity during image masking. Data augmentation is a crucial technique utilized to reduce variance in models and mitigate overfitting. Typically, there exists a trade-off between the bias and variance of a model, as they are conjugate variables. Data augmentation offers a significant advantage by reducing variance without increasing bias when the dataset size increases. Consequently, it serves as an effective method for improving model accuracy. This paper presented an approach similar to the semantic segmentation of the mask on a person's face, and therefore the same CycleGAN can be utilized to further reverse the masking of the face if needed.

The loss function to ensure semantically intact images is the adversarial loss to ensure the images being real which is followed by the cycle consistency loss for the images to semantically intact to each other. The loss function can be stated as follows

$$\mathcal{L} = \lambda_{GAN}(G, D_B, A, B) + \mathcal{L}\lambda_{GAN}(F, D_A, B, A) + \mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G, F) \quad (2.8)$$

The contribution of the paper can be seen in terms of the dataset that they have proposed using their trained model weights. The proposed dataset is known as the Masked Face Segmentation and Recognition dataset. The statistics of the dataset have been shown below [40].

Figure 2.7: Statistics of the MFSR Dataset

2.4.3.1 Proposed Dataset

The MFSR dataset proposed in the paper consists of two different subsets listed as follows.

- **Facial Mask Segmentation subset:** This part of the dataset contained around 9,742 well annotated images collected from the internet. This subset is responsible for the mask segmentation that is presented for the task of instance segmentation of the mask in the facial images. It also considers various diversity in the dataset including various pose, age variation and ethnicity. It is represented as the MFSR-SEG dataset in the image of statistics shown above.
- **MFR Benchmark Dataset:** This dataset is for the Masked Facial Recognition containing a total of 11,615 images belonging to 1,004 identities. Out of the these unique individuals 704 belong to the real-world whereas the other 300 have been obtained from the internet. The images have been filtered out to ensure it contains only the images where the face is visible and there are no contradictions in terms of the file’s reliability.

The proposed model architecture was not presented in terms of its performance with the dedicated MFR pipeline, however the paper does highlight and the product of the model that is the dataset has been released for custom training.

2.5 MFR using Attention based models

Up to this point, the discussed approaches have involved incorporating the face mask as an integral feature, treating it as a standard component, and employing generative models primarily centered around the CycleGAN architecture. One notable drawback of the generative model approach was its reliance on GAN, which inherently poses challenges due to its intractability and the instability encountered during model training, as elaborated upon with the specific issues mentioned earlier. Another approach recently adopted by the researchers is the utilization of attention-based mechanism that allow more focus on the non-occluded part in a masked facial image. These approaches are typically more time-efficient compared to their generative counterparts. With careful design, the pipeline can produce superior results, leveraging the efficiency of these methods.

2.5.1 Cropping and attention based MFR

One of the advantages of attention based modules is the utilization of the non-masked regions to be extracted from the overall masked image. This novel approach has been adopted to extract and use only the visible portion of the masked faces exclusively for MFR [41]. The cropping algorithm has been merged with the attention-based mechanism as to reduce the feature map and the input pixels to work with. Cropping, as recommended by the author, has been performed manually to ensure that all non-masked regions are accurately extracted from the original image. On the attention part, there are two different mechanisms mentioned in the proposed architecture by the authors. These are:

- Intra-channel attention mechanism
- Spatial attention mechanism

These attention layers have been used inside each of the ResNet blocks to allow attention to the desired part while extracting feature maps. The details for their implementation are as follows.

2.5.1.1 Intra-channel attention

The idea behind the attention network is to capture possible correlations among the input data image. One such dependency that can possible exist among the various channels of an RGB image. The channel attention is carried by the help of two different descriptors, obtained by the average and maxpooling respectively. The channel attention module depends only on the RGB image, so the descriptors must belong to

the vector space such as $G_{\text{avg}} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times 1 \times 1}$ and $G_{\text{max}} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times 1 \times 1}$, where G_{avg} represents average pooling and G_{max} represents max pooling. These descriptors are then fed into the Multi Layer Perceptron network which unifies them into a single embedding such that $M_c \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times 1 \times 1}$. The inclusion of MLP allows the model to have the non-linearity due to the presence of the activation function. The activation function chosen in the paper for the sake of implementation is Sigmoid, given by the equation stated below.

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2.9)$$

2.5.1.2 Spatial attention

The spatial attention in a Neural Network helps localize the object coordinates in an image. From the implementation point of view, the spatial attention layer is similar to the intra-channel attention. As in the previously discussed attention mechanism, feature descriptors are obtained using the average pooling and Maxpooling layers. The subtle difference in spatial attention is that instead of using the MLP, there is a convolutional filter kernel convolved with the descriptors, followed by the Sigmoid activation function. We have the exact implementation, except that it has utilized CNN-type convolution instead of the fully connected MLP. The detailed architecture for CBAM is as shown below [41].

Figure 2.8: Detailed architecture of the CBAM

The attention layers have been used as a modified replacement for the convolutional layers in the ResNet backbone model. Following this convention we have the modified block of convolution network as shown below [41].

Figure 2.9: Modified convolution block in ResNet-50 using CBAM block

It can be seen from the figure above that the triangular shaped module is in fact the attention modules that have been added to ensure more focus and emphasis given to the visible region of the face in an image.

2.5.1.3 Datasets

The paper cites four (4) datasets that have been utilized for the Masked Facial Recognition. These are stated as follows.

- **Simulated Masked Face Recognition Dataset (SMFRD):** This dataset contains a total of 500,000 images with the total of 10,000 identities. The masked faces have been generated using GAN in this dataset, hence the masked images are synthetic [42].
- **WebFace:** This dataset also contains a total of 500,000 images with a total of 10,000 distinct individuals. It is one of the benchmark datasets that have been used in FR tasks [43].
- **Extended Yale B:** This dataset contains diverse dataset containing images from various pose and illumination of the individual. It contains a total of 16,128 images from 28 different people under 9 poses and 64 illumination scenarios [44].
- **AR:** This is another Face Recognition dataset that contains a total of 4,000 images belonging to 126 different subjects [45].

2.5.1.4 Limitations of the architecture

The limitations in this research study have been presented below.

- The attention module have been discussed for the channel-based and spatial mode. It does solve the problem of MFR in a novel approach but the research study did not consider anything in regards to the removal of the background noise. The attention modules assumes that the input image is framed on the facial image which is generally not the case in real-time.
- The inference time of the model was not discussed in the paper. The time efficiency of the pipeline was not discussed in the research study.
- The assumption of the focused face in an image is tied to the fact that the images must be manually cropped to include the correct dimension. If these images are not copped properly due to any possible human error, it will affect the performance of the overall architecture.
- MTCNN has been used for face localization, but it was originally designed to identify unmasked face recognition [46]. For the case of masked faces, the algorithm extracts the feature pyramid, including the mask as the essential information of the face itself. This causes False Negatives in the overall detection, leading to the undermining of the overall accuracy of the model.

2.5.2 MFR using Deep Metric Learning

In terms of attention, another approach adopted by the authors in [47] is dedicated to the real-time deployment of the model. The research study has proposed a lightweight model that was utilized for both the image-based masked facial recognition and the one based on a live video stream. The model’s architecture was primarily inspired by the feature extraction layers utilized in the Face mask-based approach, as discussed in Chapter 2.3. The idea behind this simple architecture is to ensure a faster inference time for the model during deployment. The model generates a 128-dimensional feature embedding of the masked face image. The embedding is then compared with the database using the Euclidean distance for the best possible match. The MFR stage for the static image case and the live video stream have been discussed separately.

2.5.2.1 MFR in static images

The FaceMaskNet-21 proposed in the paper processes only the RGB images; therefore, every input image is converted from any other format, such as BGR, to this standard format. Using the appropriate data structure, the embedding of the faces has been stored with their corresponding identities. The embedding was considered only for the faces, and therefore, they were recorded once the coordinates of the faces had been obtained. The 128-d embedding obtained from the real-time image at the inference time have been passed through the architecture, and then compared with the database. The

choice of the loss function proposed by the authors is Euclidean distance. The model output consists of the bounding box of the person's face and its identity from the best match case in the database.

2.5.2.2 MFR in video stream and video files

The proposed pipeline, in the case of video files, segments each frame as an independent image and, therefore, uses the entire batch of images as input to the model [47]. Once the images have been batched all the standard pre-processing techniques as mentioned in the previous section. It has been stated that the currently designed architecture of the model is not sufficient to allow for live video stream-based face recognition and can only operate using the stored video file. The person is identified as "unknown" if the distance of the generated embedding is out of bounds from the known embedding in the stored database. The architecture of the proposed model is as shown below.

Figure 2.10: Detailed architecture of FaceMaskNet-21

The model architecture consists of a convolutional neural network (CNN) with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation for non-linearity, followed by cross-channel normalization. This layer indicates that the model assumes the input to be an RGB image. The remainder of the network follows a standard CNN architecture, interspersed with occasional max-pooling layers. Subsequent to the CNN, fully connected layers with 128 neurons and a softmax activation function are employed. The output encoding of the model is achieved after this output layer. The initial convolutional layers utilize larger filter kernels, sized at 55 x 55, and employ a total of 96 filter kernels. Subsequent layers maintain the same number of filter kernels but utilize smaller filter kernel sizes of 27 x 27 and then 13 x 13, with a total of 384 filters.

2.5.2.3 Datasets

The dataset used for the training of the model is mainly the state-of-the-art dataset commonly known as LFW [48]. It is a benchmark dataset for facial recognition used before the masked facial recognition research boom. 50,000 images from the dataset have been used in training of the proposed FaceMaskNet-21, with additional 204 masked images of 13 different individuals. The masked images dataset have been augmented to have a total of 2,000 images using operations such as cropping, rotation and magnification. The model was tested on the LFW dataset in a total of 325 instances. The model was found to be working correctly for a total of 289 instances, yielding an overall accuracy of 88.92%.

The inference time of the model has been measured using the custom dataset having a total of 1,192 images belonging to 13 different individuals. The inference time of the model have been recorded against the different type of resolution in the test dataset. The time of inference is as tabulated below.

Table 2.4. Execution time for different input image resolutions

Input Resolution	Average Execution Time (seconds)
128x128	3.58
227x227	9.54
512x512	18.66
1024x1024	45.6

The inference time of the model state in the table is for a single image rather than the batch of images. Therefore, the inference time for a video file can be obtained against its resolution based upon its length as it translates to the number of captured frames.

2.5.2.4 Limitations of the architecture

The discussed pipeline presents a novelty by focusing on the real-time implementation of the Masked Facial Recognition. A special focus and attention have been given to the inference time of the model under various input image resolutions. That being said, there are a few issues that have not been addressed in the pipeline. The limitations for the model have been stated below.

- Starting from the training phase of the model, the dataset distribution for the model into the corresponding training and test dataset is not valid. A good rule of thumb in CV-related tasks is to have a test and a development set that contains at least around 5,000 to 10,000 images for larger datasets; in the case of smaller datasets, the conventional partition of 60%, 20%, 20% for training, development and test dataset. However, the model was tested on only 325 instances of the LFW dataset, and the custom dataset containing 1,192 images for all the training, development, and test sets has been used. There needs to be more than this dataset to validate the performance of a model.
- The pipeline designed for the MFR is kept very simple to ensure faster inference time of the model. In pursuit of a time-efficient model, the overall system needed to be simplified, leaving room for potential improvements in accuracy. The presented model does not feature the Batch Normalization layer, which allows not only the model to accelerate in the training process but also caters to the problem of covariate shifting [49]. The lack of a Batch Normalization layer and the fact that the model has been tested on a limited dataset can be a serious bottleneck in ensuring the reliable performance of the model when deployed.
- The architecture did not consider any technique for "Face Verification". This step is preliminary for real-time applications as the captured image or a frame in a video is likely to contain background noise. Without focusing on the face completely, the architecture is not robust enough to ensure reliable face recognition, barring masked and other pose variations.
- The video streaming detection requires the video to be saved rather than working on the live stream itself, as in some state-of-the-art YOLO models, such as the recent YOLOv9 [51]. This accounts for the need for a reliable feature in the model pipeline keeping in view the real-time deployment of the model.
- There are not much discussion with regards to the post-processing of the model to ensure its deployment. Techniques such as quantization, model-pruning helps in the inference time of the model.

- The reported inference time of the model, even for the lowest resolution image in the experiment that, is 128 x 128, is 3.58 seconds, which is not suitable for a real-time application such as surveillance. The model can, however, be used for more passive applications such as attendance systems or ticketing systems in parks.

2.6 Diverse Approaches for Masked Face Recognition

In the preceding sections, we explored recent research endeavors in Masked Facial Recognition. These studies have been categorized based on the types of architectures they employ, as discussed in detail earlier. Many of the algorithms and techniques prominently utilized for Masked Face Recognition have been incorporated in some variant within the pipelines we've discussed, whether through Batch Normalization, specific loss functions, or adaptations of generative or attention-based models. However, the algorithms discussed in this section represent a distinct set that neither fits into the previously designated categories nor has been employed in any form throughout the entire pipelines discussed thus far. These architectures are also implemented in various research studies, showcasing notable methods for handling facial image datasets. We will now discuss each of them individually in the following section to follow.

2.6.1 Siamese Networks

Siamese Networks represent a type of Neural Network specifically designed for comparing input data, typically images, in terms of their similarity [52]. In essence, a Machine Learning model can be viewed as a complex and highly non-linear mathematical function. Like any other mathematical function, given the same weights and biases, it's expected that identical inputs will consistently yield the same outputs. This forms the fundamental concept behind Siamese Networks. They consist of a pair of Neural networks that share their weights and are updated simultaneously using the same hyperparameters and gradients computed during backpropagation. If the output of both models given two images is the same or falls within a certain threshold, it indicates that the images are indeed the same or exhibit a high degree of similarity. A common implementation of weight sharing in Siamese networks is illustrated below [53]. It can be seen that the architecture is nothing but an identical Neural Network replicated twice by implementing the weights and bias sharing techniques. One practical implementation of this architecture involves utilizing a single Neural Network and feeding it with pairs of targeted images, with the network sharing the same weights for both inputs. In this setup, the model receives image pairs sequentially rather than simultaneously. This approach allows for the use of a single Neural Network instead of twin pairs, providing flexibility in the implementation.

Figure 2.11: Weights and Bias sharing in Siamese Networks

The block diagram illustrated above for a Neural Network represents another option for object detection. As with any other case, the suitability of this approach depends heavily on the nature of the problem and the complexity of objectives to be achieved, such as time efficiency or model accuracy. Different architectures may be preferred based on specific requirements and constraints of the task at hand. One of the recent implementations of the network for One-shot learning has been presented in [54]. The architecture is shown below.

Figure 2.12: Architecture of the One-shot Siamese Network

It can be seen from the NN shown above that it consists of the basic CNN followed by the necessary non-linear layers required to allow the model to attain pattern recognition for complex datasets. The network in [54] was a generic representation of many possibilities for different tasks including Facial recognition or even Masked Facial Recognition. One of the key advantages of Siamese Networks is their flexible architecture, which enables the modeling and solution of various problems. By adding a final layer followed by a sigmoid activation function, the network can be transformed into a binary classification problem. Similarly, by using softmax activation, it can address multi-class classification problems. Furthermore, the same trained network can be leveraged to address open-class problems, such as Masked Facial Recognition

(MFR) in many cases. This adaptability makes Siamese Networks a versatile choice for a range of tasks.

2.6.1.1 Advantages of Siamese Networks

The advantages of the Siamese Networks have been listed below.

- **Class Imbalance:** An added advantage of these networks is their robustness to class imbalance in the dataset. The architecture of the network has been designed to ensure that even in case of limited dataset for a particular class the learning can be carried out effectively.
- **One-shot learning:** Siamese networks are inherently one-show learners much like YOLO. This makes them one of the faster ways to detect and recognize objects such as faces in a typical face recognition problem.
- **Semantic Similarity:** Unlike the common classification networks, Siamese networks work on the principle of extracting feature embedding from the input image. The output is the feature vector rather than the output class number. The feature vectors can be further stored in a database as both the useful and compressed representation of the original image.

2.6.1.2 Loss Functions

Siamese Networks operate by comparing the feature embedding of the input data with the corresponding label. The label in this case is also an embedding for the known entity. The dimensionality of the acquired feature vector depends on the number of neurons in the output layer. It should be the same as that of the ones stored in the database for comparison's sake. The common choices for the loss function in case of Siamese Networks have been discussed as under.

- **Contrastive Loss:** This loss function is based on the distance metric among the feature embedding [55]. It assumes that the model is comparing a pair of images in order to ensure that the images belonging to the same person are pushed closer and the unrelated images are separated in the feature space. The distance metric most commonly used in the process is the Euclidean Distance as shown below.

$$D_w(X_1, X_2) = \|G_w(X_1) - G_w(X_2)\|^2 \quad (2.10)$$

The above equation computes the distance among the feature vectors, but it does not include any penalty terms in case the model predicts the output wrong. The pairwise implementation of the Contrastive Loss function has been shown below.

$$L(W, Y, X_1, X_2) = \frac{1}{2}[(1 - Y) \cdot D_w^2 + Y \cdot \max(0, m - D_w)^2] \quad (2.11)$$

The loss function includes the term 'm' which indicates the margin. This ensures that there is a certain distance among the dissimilar feature vectors in a feature space. In the above loss function the value of 'Y' indicates the label for each sample image. If both the images belong to the same person then the value of Y = 0, which means that the loss function is reduced to the following equation.

$$L(W, Y, X_1, X_2) = \frac{1}{2}D_w^2 \quad (2.12)$$

The above equation is essentially the half of the Euclidean Distance stated in equation 2.10. It means that the penalty on the Neural Network is only dependent on the distance among the feature vectors of the similar images. However, in case of dissimilar images the loss function is reduced to the following equation.

$$L(W, Y, X_1, X_2) = \frac{1}{2}[Y \cdot \max(0, m - D_w)^2] \quad (2.13)$$

The margin introduced in the above equation ensures that there is at least 'm' units of distance among the unrelated feature embedding. It is not a hyper parameter but the threshold that can be set to have the desired results. For instance, in case of sensitive application such as surveillance system the threshold can be set to high ensuring that the predictive model has to be absolutely sure to be able to classify the person as "wanted". In other less sensitive applications such as ticketing system in the park the threshold can be adjust to a slightly lower value to ensure faster training process. The total loss function for all the training examples can be computed by the cumulative sum over the entire set of example images.

$$L(W) = \sum_{i=1}^P L(W, (Y, X_1, X_2)^*) \quad (2.14)$$

- **Triplet Loss:** The Triplet loss is based on the triplet of images rather than the pair of them [56]. The images are labelled as the Anchor, the Positive, and the Negative example. The idea behind this loss function is to improve the contrastive loss function by increasing the distance between the anchor and the negative example while simultaneously decreasing the Euclidean distance between the anchor and the positive example. The main objective of the loss function is to ensure that the distance of the feature embedding inside a feature space is such that the anchor and the positive example are closer than the anchor and the

negative example image. Therefore, the mathematical relation for the objective function can be stated as follows.

$$L(a, p, n) = \max\{d(a, p) - d(a, n) + \alpha, 0\} \quad (2.15)$$

In the above equation, $d(a,p)$ is the Euclidean distance among the positive and anchor image, whereas $d(a,n)$ is the distance among the anchor image and the negative example image. ' α ' is the margin term that sets out a threshold as to how much the positive and the negative example images must be set apart from the anchor image. The application of the margin and how it helps in the separability of the embedding in the feature space can be demonstrated by the image shown below [57].

Figure 2.13: A demonstration of margin in the Triplet Loss Function

From the above image, it can be demonstrated that the training of the Siamese Networks with respect to the Triplet Loss function is carried out in a way that sets the negative examples further apart from the anchor compared to the positive example by at least the amount of the magnitude of the margin term α included in the loss function as shown in equation 2.15. Just as in the case of the contrastive loss function, the term can be varied during the network training, depending upon the application for which the model was trained.

2.6.1.3 Limitations of the architecture

Although Siamese Networks offer an excellent pipeline for ensuring the mapping of the masked and the unmasked face images, it needs to include the following limitations in its implementation.

- **Extensive Dataset:** The dataset must be prepared, and the availability of the paired datasets must be ensured in order to train these networks. This is because

both the contrastive and the triplet loss functions depend on the image pairs, if not the triplets, for training the model. For the sake of MFR, the image for both the masked and the unmasked face image must be present in order to train the model.

- **Difficult training:** The problem with the Triplet Loss function is explicitly ensuring that the dataset contains hard enough triplet examples for the network to be effectively trained. In the case of a relatively straightforward set of examples, it would be easier for the model to distinguish among the examples, and the learning would not be effective as the model might not be able to perform well when deployed. This accounts for the dataset to be prepared cautiously, ensuring that the examples are not randomly picked but prepared to provide better model performance.
- **Longer Training:** The training of the Siamese Networks is a computationally complex task and therefore it demands for the powerful GPU and longer training times.
- **Sensitivity to Imbalance Dataset:** The requirement of the loss function utilized in Siamese Networks demands the availability of the data pairs that need to be mapped against each other. In case of an imbalanced dataset with some examples missing the image pairs, the network will not be able to pair the single images. Therefore, the training for the particular example image will be halted.

2.6.2 Ensemble Models

Considering the pros and cons of the techniques discussed in the previous section, a common approach for improvement would be to utilize the ensemble models. One such example presented in [58] is the utilization of Transformer models followed by the convolution and fully connected networks. The architecture for the model has been presented below.

Figure 2.14: Architecture of the Ensemble model

The architecture has been presented to process each part of the image separately. The transformer network for the image encoding has been inspired by Dosovitskiy et al [59]. The idea for the transformer network is to ensure that the input image is divided into patches so that the individual patches can be processed independently. The division of the images into the patches distorts the spatial information of the image and therefore the positional embedding have been inserted into the network for proper ordering. Once the patches have been developed, the smaller images have been passed into the rest of the network for feature extraction and attention based learning. The networks has been designed in the way that the patched images have been processed using the Batch Normalization layer, CNN , and finally it feeds into the fully connected layer. The first block into the network has a different Multi-Headed Attention layer inspired from the transformer. Once the attention have been established, the features can be extracted as normal.

The last layer of the network contains the fully connected layer with the softmax activation function that computes the probability of the person's identity given the total number of person in the original database. The usage of softmax ensures that the architecture for the model is in fact well suited for the closed-class problem. The utilization of the positional embedding at the start is utilized later on in the pipeline for the proper ordering of the patches into the complete image.

2.6.2.1 Dataset

The dataset utilized in this paper is the well-known benchmark known as the LFW dataset. The overall dataset used in the training of the model included around 25,000 images with a total of 5,749 subjects. The accuracy achieved for the proposed ensemble model was less compared to the other models. The authors attribute the lesser accuracy towards the nature of the LFW dataset where 4,047 subjects out of the total 5,749 contains only a single image.

2.6.2.2 Limitations of the architecture

The drawbacks of the proposed architecture have been briefed as follows.

- The model under performed when tested on the LFW dataset depicting the underfitting caused by the training of the architecture
- The paper presented no grounds towards the inference time or real-time deployment of the pipeline
- The architecture could have been improved with the utilization of pre-trained transformers instead of training the model on limited dataset.

2.7 Datasets in MFR

It is only possible to train a state-of-the-art Deep Learning model with a refined and cleaned dataset. All of the better models have a common feature: they exhibit the utilization of a better set of data for the training. This section presents the most commonly used datasets in Masked Face Recognition. Although the datasets have been mentioned alongside the discussed approaches and the paper, this section will explore holistically the available datasets for the convenience of the reader. The datasets have been compiled as shown in the table below.

Table 2.5. Summary of the common MFR benchmarking datasets

Dataset	Size (Images)	Identities	Types of Masks
RMFRD [60]	95,000	525	Real-world
SMFRD [60]	500,000	10,000	Synthetic
MFSR [40]	11,615	1,004	Real-world / Synthetic
LFW-SM [37]	13,233	5,749	Synthetic
MFR2 [37]	269	53	Synthetic
MFV [61]	400	200	Synthetic
MFI [61]	4,916	669	Synthetic
MFD [62]	990	45	Synthetic
MFW-mini [63]	3,000	300	Synthetic
CelebA [64]	>200 K	10,177	Synthetic
CelebA-HQ [65]	>30 K	307	Synthetic
MS1MV2-Masked [66]	5.8 M	85,000	Synthetic
CFP-FP	7,000	500	Synthetic
CFP-FF	7,000	500	Synthetic
CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0 [67]	17,580	725	Synthetic
Oulu-CASIA NIR-VIS [68]	7,680	80	Synthetic
BUAA-VisNir [69]	2,700	150	Synthetic
CASIA-FaceV5 [70]	2,500	500	Synthetic
VGG-Face _{2_m} [71]	3.3 M	9,131	Synthetic
Webface [72]	500 K	10,000	Synthetic
AR [73]	4,000	126	Synthetic
Extend Yela B [74]	16,128	28	Synthetic
AgeDB [75]	16,488	568	Real-world

A total of 23 benchmark datasets have been reported and published as open-source. These datasets are important as all of the papers utilise the derivatives of these datasets for the evaluation and performance verification of the trained models. The proposed

model in this thesis has also been evaluated based on the derivatives of the mentioned dataset.

2.8 Post-processing for Model Deployment

There needs to be more than the training of the model to ensure a reliable deployment for real-time applications. The idea of the post-processing of an already trained model has been borrowed from the recent open-source deep-learning architectures that utilize billions of parameters [76]. With the exponential increase in the number of parameters, there needs to be equivalently suitable hardware in terms of the GPU for loading the model and processing it correctly. One such study has been shown below [76].

Figure 2.15: Exponential Growth of the model size over time

It can be visualized from the graph above that the model size risen exponentially to the point when it is almost impossible for the large models to be accessed on the available hardware. The concept can also be utilized for the case of MFR application in order to deploy the model on an AI accelerated board such as Jetson Xavier AGX for efficient implementation on the CUDA cores. Not only does it help in the faster inference time of the model, but it also ensures that the accuracy of the model is retained within acceptable limits. The AI-based hardware is generally designed for the

installation as an independent node to be utilized in a greater mesh network. This accounts for limited storage memory and the constraints on power consumption asking for the model to be optimized for practical use. The model optimization techniques have been discussed in the upcoming section.

2.8.1 Model Quantization

The training of the model consists of tuning the weights and biases in order to achieve the desired result. These quantities are expressed in a matrix consisting of numbers that are usually floating point, most commonly FP32 standard. FP32 standard ensures that each individual weight and bias requires a total of 4 bytes each for storage. This size also translates in the computational complexity of the model as these matrices are utilized in the computation of the desired activations. A possible way to solve this problem is to quantize the model weights into other data types that are more supportive of the intended hardware. It ensure less computational time for the algorithm with the same computational complexity. The data types for the storage of model weights and biases have been compared as follows.

Table 2.6. Floating-Point Datatype Characteristics

Datatype	Precision	Maximum
FP32	Best	$\sim 10^{38}$
FP16	Better	$\sim 10^4$
BF16	Good	$\sim 10^{38}$

From the above table it can be concluded that the default data type most commonly used by the Deep Learning models offers the best precision with a high maximum value. In the default configuration a single weight parameter requires a space of 4 bytes. For a large model that has billions of parameters the memory of the device can be easily exhausted leading to the real-time application being crashed in the production cycle. The details of the number of bits assignment for the different floating points have been stated below.

Table 2.7. Bitwise allocation for floating point variants

Format	Sign	Exponent	Fraction	Min (approx.)	Max (approx.)
FP16	1	5	10	-6.10×10^{-5}	6.55×10^4
FP32	1	8	23	-3.40×10^{38}	3.40×10^{38}
BF16	1	8	7	-3.39×10^{38}	3.39×10^{38}

The exponent is the range of the floating point; the greater the number of bits for the exponent, the more outstanding the minimum to maximum range for the number.

Based on the stated table, it can be deduced that the model compression can be achieved by down-changing the data type of the model from FP32 to either BF16 or FP16. The quantization achieved in this manner is a naive-based approach as it does not ensure that the accuracy of the model is conserved while attempting to compress the model. To ensure little to no drop in the model's accuracy, the linear quantization technique is most commonly used in SOTA machine learning models [77]. Using the linear quantization technique, the FP32 standard for the weights and biases can be reduced to the integer data type for 8 bits each. The quantization has been explained as shown below.

2.8.1.1 Linear Quantization

In linear quantization, the mapping among the 32-bit floating point and the 8-bit integer have been mapped using a linear transformation. The mapping of the data types in the case of model quantization from FP32 to 8-bit integers have been shown below [78].

Figure 2.16: Mapping of FP32 to 8-bit integer

The concept have been borrowed from the field of signal processing much similar to the mapping of the analog signal frequencies onto the digital frequencies. The range of frequencies from $-\frac{F_s}{2}$ to $\frac{F_s}{2}$ are mapped onto $-\pi$ to π using a linear transformation [79]. The floating point numbers mentioned in the figure shown above represents the maximum and the minimum values for the weights and biases under consideration. One of the most common transformation from the floating point to integer parameters is the absmax quantization [80]. The mathematical relation for 8-bit quantization have been stated as follows.

$$X_{\text{quant}} = \text{round} \left(\frac{127}{\max|x|} \cdot x \right) \quad (2.16)$$

where X_{quant} is the quantized parameter attained after the absmax linear transformation. One common issue with quantization is that it inherits a lossy nature; therefore, the model is often re-trained to counter the issues to ensure accuracy. From the implementation point of view the model quantization can be carried out either during or after the formal training. In either cases the reverse of the quantization on the parameters can be performed for 8-bit integers by the following equation.

$$X_{\text{dequant}} = \left(\frac{\max|x|}{127} \right) \cdot X_{\text{quant}} \quad (2.17)$$

2.8.1.2 Post-training quantization vs Quantization Aware training

Post-training and quantization aware training are the 2 most common implementation of the model’s parameter quantization. A detailed comparison of the implementation techniques have been shared in the following table.

Table 2.8. Comparison between Post-training Quantization and Quantization-aware Training

Aspect	Post-training Quantization	Quantization-aware Training
Model performance	Usually slightly lower	Typically higher retention of accuracy
Training process	Quantization after training	Quantization incorporated during training
Accuracy loss	Higher loss due to post-training quantization	Lower loss due to awareness during training
Model compatibility	Can be applied to already trained models	Requires retraining or training from scratch
Complexity	Simpler implementation	May require more complex optimization techniques

It is more common to employ the stated equation 2.16 and 2.17 simultaneously when training with awareness to quantization, however a major drawback is that it is not possible to re-train the larger backbone models in the architecture. Post-training allows the flexibility of utilizing the backbone models without having to re-train at the cost of some small margin of accuracy [81].

2.8.2 Model Pruning

Pruning is another common technique utilized for model compression. In model pruning the less contributing parameters of the model are pruned out in order to make the weights matrix sparse leading to faster implementation at the inference time [82]. As almost all of the learnable parameters comprise the weights matrix, this technique is implemented only on the weights, and the biases are left as they are. Similar to the model parameters quantization technique, the pruning of a model can be carried out either during training or on the already trained model. Model pruning is carried out similarly to the convolution layer operation in a CNN. A dedicated filter kernel is utilized to ensure the unnecessary parameters are zeroed out, ensuring the model is lightweight and good for deployment. A demonstration of such an operation has been shared below [83].

Figure 2.17: A post-training demonstration of model parameter pruning

The bit-mask presented in this case is used to mask the weight matrix's second column, resulting in sparse entries. In practical scenarios, there are available libraries much like the implementation of Deep Learning models in the form of Tensorflow or PyTorch in Python and Caffe in C++ to ensure the implementation of the model optimization technique, including model quantization and pruning of the weights and the biases [84,85,86]. Model pruning is a concept mostly borrowed from the Dropout and is frequently used in Computer Vision due to the immense dataset required to

ensure no overfitting [87]. Dropout assumes no importance to any of the weights while considering neglecting it as it selects randomly as to what percentage of neurons needs to be dropped. Contrary to this model, pruning is attention-based, and it utilizes the model’s parameters that are close to zero (0) to be dropped as they compare the least in terms of the model’s output. This phenomenon allows model pruning to be done either during the training or post-training each with its own pros and cons. This choice of the implementation have been discussed as follows.

2.8.2.1 Pruning Aware Training vs post-training model pruning

The advantages and drawbacks of the implementation of these techniques have been discussed as follows.

Table 2.9. Comparison of Post-Model Pruning and Model Pruning During Training

Aspect	Post-Model Pruning	Model Pruning During Training
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplifies the model after training without retraining. • Can be applied to pre-trained models. • Can achieve significant compression rates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporates pruning directly into the training process, potentially leading to better final performance. • Can result in smaller model sizes compared to post-model pruning.
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May require fine-tuning or retraining to restore performance. • May not achieve the same level of compression as pruning during training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires modification of training procedures and algorithms. • May introduce additional complexity to the training process.

As mentioned above, a significant problem with the model pruning carried out during the model’s training is that the objective function’s gradients need to be more deterministic as a function of the model parameter. This is because the backward

propagation step is entirely unaware of the weights that have been dropped. Therefore, there is a problem as the path of the gradients to flow back to the input data has been terminated by making the network parameters sparse. Furthermore, in the case of model pruning the weights and biases are meant to be permanently made sparse preferably at the time of inference which is different when compared to dropout. As with the increase in the number of epochs for a given pattern of the learning rate, the model pruning during the training time of the model ensures a more steady output. A learning curve for the stated phenomenon have been shown below [88].

Figure 2.18: Post training model pruning vs Pruning aware model training

2.8.3 Knowledge Distillation

So far, the model optimization techniques, namely, model pruning and quantization, have been discussed. Both methods primarily focus on optimizing the model by reducing the memory storage of the weights and biases or dropping out the non-contributing parameters. Knowledge Distillation differs from the methods above as it involves 2 different Neural Networks where the smaller network learns to mimic the prediction of the bigger model [89]. The size of the smaller model can be treated as a hyperparameter depending upon the application, as it is responsible for the accuracy vs computational complexity tradeoff. The learning of the model involves a teacher or the cumbersome model that is well trained on the desired dataset. The simpler network often referred to as the student model inherits the learning from the larger model. This techniques, however assumes the following constraints:

- The training and the validation dataset for both the teacher and the student model are the same
- The dataset labels are standard among and shared among the more prominent and the student model.

- The teacher model has been trained thoroughly on the dataset without possible overfitting. In this case, the weights and biases of the more extensive network are optimal; if they are sub-optimal, they can act as a potential bottleneck in the designed pipeline.
- The teacher model also shares its "soft targets" with the student model. This allows the training of the smaller model to be accelerated and pushed towards faster convergence. The final layer extracts the "soft targets" of the model before applying the softmax activation function.
- In the case of an open-class classification model, the feature embedding of the input data can be shared as it ensures the reduced dimension representation of the same input image. For algorithms that involve classical algorithms such as PCA, the feature vector with the reduced dimensionality reduction can be utilized to learn the smaller network and the labels in the original dataset.

An exciting aspect of this technique is that the architecture of the smaller network is not bound to be similar to that of the more extensive network. Knowledge Distillation, therefore, allows the learning of the more extensive network to be translated into the smaller student network, effectively reducing the model's size. The depiction of the implementation of the technique can be demonstrated as shown in the figure below [90].

Figure 2.19: Knowledge Distillation from teacher to the student network

The figure demonstrates the utilization of the Artificial Neural Network. However, the concept can be expanded to more complicated models. An essential consideration of the network is ensuring that the size reduction ratio of the teacher and the student

model is within the acceptable range. For instance, a shallow Neural Network comprising a couple of Dense layers cannot adequately learn the knowledge distillation of a SOTA network such as VGG-19. There are various implementation for knowledge distillation aimed to compress the model size while retaining the performance. Few of the most common techniques have been discussed in the coming section.

2.8.3.1 Adversarial Knowledge Distillation

Inspired by Generative Adversarial Networks, one possible way to implement Knowledge Distillation is to ensure the adversarial training of the teacher and the student Neural Network. Although it is possible to train the larger and the smaller Neural Networks simultaneously, the main idea of Knowledge Distillation is to ensure model compression rather than training to prevent adversarial attacks [91]. The concept of adversarial training is to ensure that the larger model can learn something new, while the smaller model can be used to learn the previously learned parameters of the model. This can be achieved by randomly providing the model with new data instances and data on which the larger model has already been trained, ensuring the "soft targets" are well within the learning of the teacher model. This process can improve while the larger model continues to learn and transfer its knowledge to the smaller model that is trying to mimic the performance of the state-of-the-art (SOTA) model.

2.8.3.2 Multi-teacher Distillation

The multi-teacher knowledge distillation is utilized for the efficient learning of the student network by combining the learned features of more than one teacher model. This is essential in the case of the Ensemble model approach where the models have been trained to learn several patterns from the input data independently [92,93,94]. It also helps in the learning of various modalities as each of the models can be utilized for the learning of different domains of the dataset rather than the features alone, such as high-level or low-level features. For instance, in the application of autonomous vehicles, there are various modalities involved, including visual data from cameras, LiDAR data for depth perception, and sensor data for environmental factors. By incorporating multiple teacher models trained on different modalities, the student network can effectively learn from diverse sources of information, enhancing its overall performance and robustness. This is in fact one of the most common approaches used in practice for complicated tasks such as the one described above. In the case of Masked Facial Recognition in its current state, Knowledge Distillation can be particularly useful for a variety of features. One teacher model could focus on mask segmentation learning, while the other on mapping the input data onto the feature space. It becomes quite interesting and yields promising results, knowing that the training of various large models for extracting different features and operating on different datasets can be utilized for

learning a unified representation of all these models. The interaction of the student models with a bunch of cumbersome models have been shown in the figure below [90].

Figure 2.20: Multi-teacher knowledge Distillation

The idea of incorporating post-training optimization technique can indeed result in the overall computational efficiency of the model while maintaining the same accuracy. In the use-case of this thesis it is preliminary as the model is intended for deployment on the hardware in order to ensure reliable performance in real-time application.

Chapter 3

Methods and Methodology

This thesis presents a novel approach for real-time Masked Facial Recognition. The critical analysis from the literature review of the concerned topic has led to the adaptation of the positive impacts of the pipeline above and improvements to their adverse effects. Since the algorithm emphasizes the real-time implementation of the MFR pipeline, particular focus has been given to the model optimization techniques and the CUDA core optimization on the dedicated hardware. As discussed in the section below, a mismatch in any optimization strategies may lead to adverse performances even when compared to an ordinary CPU [95,96]. Starting from the developed pipeline, this chapter is focused on the insights for the model developed, process management, bottleneck analysis and finally, the implementation results on the Jetson Xavier AGX. The entire pipeline has been discussed in the block-wise scenario, where each single block is responsible for learning a specific task that eventually contributes to the more significant cause of Masked Facial Recognition. A detailed analysis of the drawbacks of all the previous architecture, such as background noise, lack of face verification and a robust pipeline for a reliable face generation that is also semantically correlated with the visible part of the face. The hardware and real-time model deployment with an external camera demand specific analytical changes to the architecture discussed in the following section.

3.1 Overview of the MFR pipeline

Masked Facial Recognition is a complex task requiring the development of a complete pipeline rather than a simple Neural Network as in the case of regression or classification. The designed pipeline is a tree-like tree-like, depending on the need for the analysis or the user's requirement. An ensemble model-based approach allows for the tradeoff between the model's accuracy and the timing efficiency of the model. An analysis has been made for the attention-based and generative models to ensure optimal

performance during deployment. For the sake of convenience and further discussion, the overall sketch of the developed pipeline have been reiterated as shown below.

Figure 3.1: Outline of the proposed model architecture

The individual block stages for the pipelines designed have been listed as follows:

- Face Verification stage.
- A decision stage to account for the tradeoff between the model's accuracy and the computational complexity.
- A generative model-based pipeline based on the conditional Denoising Diffusion Implicit Models to reconstruct the masked face. This is followed by the backbone model to map the reconstructed face onto the feature space.
- An attention-based model scheme for the extraction of the feature embedding based on the attention-based model followed by the loss function that optimizes the geodesic distance
- The availability of a database that can be accessed in real-time with a linear time complexity or less.

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3.2 Face Verification stage

One of the foremost and essential elements of the Face Recognition or Masked Face recognition model is using the face verification step. It enables us to remove the background noise and focus more on extracting the features of the relevant part of the image. In real-time, a picture might contain more than one face, and therefore, the face verification steps need to be robust, and negligence in developing this type of model can lead to a severe bottleneck. This is because when an MFR model is deployed in real-time, the camera will capture some extra background noise, and running a feature extractor model right away might hinder the model’s output [97]. The face verification stage in the pipeline above is the same for the entire ensemble model, including the generative and attention-based models. Face verification aims to accurately localize any N number of faces in an image, whether masked or unmasked, from the complete image captured by the camera in real time. In the previous architectures, a number of face verification models, including the MTCNN, SSH, PCN, and Tiny Face detector [9,98,99,100]. All these face detectors, in general, and MTCNN in particular, have been used widely as state-of-the-art face detection algorithms. However, all these algorithms were developed in the pre-COVID era and used to detect faces when presented in an unoccluded form precisely.

Considering the problem of Masked Facial Recognition, the choice of face localization or verification step features the famous RetinaFace model. The initially proposed architecture of RetinaFace comes with many more features than simple face localization. It has been widely used for 3D face construction, given 2D images of the face, face location and bounding box regression [101]. For the use case in our pipeline, only the face localization part of the feature has been given due importance. The face detection part in RetinaFace, much to the benefit and advantage of our application, has been carried out in a single shot, so the algorithm is efficient and reliable enough to work with real-time deployment. The architecture for the face localization step consists of the following three (3) blocks.

- **Feature Pyramid Network:** This network stage is responsible for applying the Convolutional Neural Network with varying filter sizes by constructing the

five (5) pyramid features of resized images. This is one of the critical steps for ensuring that all the faces in a photo of any given size are detectable in an image. The feature pyramids have been extracted using the ResNet model, which has been trained to extract the features from images [35].

- **Context Head Module:** This module is one of the significant blocks in ensuring reliable face detection in masked and unmasked faces. It utilizes the Deformable Convolution Network to ensure that the features have been extracted from different locations rather than a set of localized grids inside an image. It helps and acts as the attention mechanism as the information is routed in the entire image space rather than being confined in the grid size of the small patch of the images that is equal to the filter size. The deformed convolutional approach have been depicted as shown in the figure below [102].

Figure 3.2: Standard Convolution vs Deformable Convolutional Neural Network

It can be verified that the distortion in the selection of pixels for the computation is unstructured in the case of DCN leading to the flow of information across the image. It is important as the masked faces will require more information from the unobscured parts of the faces.

- **Classification step:** This part of the architecture is responsible for the binary classification of whether the face has been detected. Based on the IoU metric, the algorithm determines the region of union among the detected faces by the bounding face regression and the ground truth. The decision criterion chosen in the paper is as follows:

$$f(\text{IoU}) = \begin{cases} \textit{positive} & \text{if } \text{IoU} \geq 0.7 \\ \textit{negative} & \text{if } \text{IoU} \leq 0.5 \\ \textit{ignored} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

These configurations allow the model to accurately determine the coordinates of the face even in the wild. Another important aspect of the model is that have been trained on the WIDER Face dataset [103]. It contains a wide range of faces for facial detection under challenging circumstances including occlusion, pose variations, and lighting changes. A subset of images from this dataset have been shared as follows.

Figure 3.3: A subset of images in the WIDER Face dataset

The images in the WIDER face dataset can be to have a diverse group of images from a single face localization example to multiple faces including the faces with occlusion. RetinaFace utilizes the multi-task loss function. For the face localization we have the following.

$$L = L_{cls}(p_i, p) + \lambda_1 L_{box}(t_i, t) + \lambda_2 L_{pts}(l_i, l) + \lambda_3 L_{pixel} \quad (3.1)$$

In the above equation we have four (4) terms included in the objective function that have been explained as follows.

- $L_{cls}(p_i, p)$: This term represents the softmax classification loss for the network. It is a binary loss that determines whether there is the face of a person present in the image or not.
- $\lambda_1 L_{box}(t_i, t)$: It represents the bounding box regression loss for the face detection. This part of the algorithm is important as it involves the precise localization of the images forming an integral computational block in the overall MFR pipeline.

- $\lambda_2 L_{pts}(l_i, l)$: To ensure the localization of the face even in the case of occlusion and pose estimation the algorithm utilizes 5 different facial landmark features including eyes, jawlines on both sides of the face, eye brows, nose and lips.
- $\lambda_3 L_{pixel}$: It is the pixel wise loss with respect to the ground truth. This loss is responsible to ensure that the predicted face along with the bounding box is well-within the threshold of tolerance.

3.2.1 Choice of the Face Verification block

The choice of RetinaFace for the face verification step has been inspired by the results of other well-known facial detectors, including MTCNN, tiny face detectors, and SSH, as reported in earlier studies. Furthermore, it has been noticed in practice that only the RetinaFace includes facial landmark-based detection and the modern Deep Learning-based approach, which allowed the hybrid model to be utilized efficiently in our case of masked facial recognition. A small recollection of the comparison of other detectors with the RetinaFace have been presented in the table below.

Table 3.1. Comparison of Face Detection Methods for Masked FR

Architecture	Description	Speed vs. Acc	Masked FR Potential
Tiny Face Detector	Lightweight model optimized for small faces.	Very fast, lower accuracy on complex scenes.	Limited. Mainly focuses on small faces.
SSH	Context-aware detector using multiple scales.	Good balance of speed and accuracy.	Moderate. Can handle partial occlusion but not designed for it.
RetinaFace	Robust to occlusion and pose variation.	Moderately fast, high accuracy.	Good. Explicitly designed for various occlusions.
MTCNN	Landmark-based, cascaded approach.	Slower, but very accurate for unoccluded faces.	Poor. Highly reliant on facial landmarks, disrupted by masks.

Most of the detectors have been designed explicitly for facial recognition, with more emphasis on lighting and pose variations. The more classical approaches,

including HOG-based features, concluded that they were less efficient than the modern detectors involving machine learning models, which have surpassed their statistical counterparts. Recently, one of the most widely used face detection algorithms have been MTCNN and RetinaFace, but the architecture of the RetinaFace as discussed earlier focuses more on the face using the context head module and is also a single shot algorithm so it supports the face extraction process in MFR applications. Both the implementations have been carried out on the faces in the wild; a small subset of the overall test have been as shown in the figure below, as conducted in our experiment. The subset contains all the aspects including the pose variation, diverse ethnicity and multiple faces located at distance with background noise.

Figure 3.4: Performance comparison of MTCNN vs RetinaFace on Masked Faces in the wild

It can be observed that the application of the RetinaFace model, even on the lowest of the possible pixels and resolution of the image, allows multiple detection of the faces when masked compared to MTCNN as verified in the first 2 images from the input test dataset. Furthermore, the time consumed by MTCNN was 174 milliseconds for the image of the most significant resolution, 318 x 159. In contrast,

RetinaFace took around 20 milliseconds, making it faster at the inference time due to the single-shot nature.

3.3 Inference time based architecture selector

The choice of pipeline at the time of deployment was made based on the inference time. The Python script used for the deployment allows the user with extra tags to select the accuracy vs tradeoff. The decision could have also been made independently based on the application. For instance, in the case of a sensitive application with fewer stakes on the inference time, one can focus more on the Diffusion model-based pipeline and even combine the results of both the diffusion model and the attention-based mechanism. However, the face detection is joint to both pipelines; therefore, only the pre-processed images are fed into the model. In the case of multiple faces, the images are fed into batches, and the optimization algorithm with the mini-batch processing has been implemented—mini-batch optimizers, including the Gradient Descent and the Adam optimizer, allow faster model parameter convergence. Therefore, the input image fed into the model has the feature dimension $\eta_X = (p_H, p_W, 3, m)$ where 'm' is the number of face images extracted from the input image depending on the number of detected faces.

3.4 Denoising Diffusion Implicit Models

Another model employed in the pipeline is the Denoising Diffusion Implicit Model (DDIM), specifically designed to generate unoccluded face images from masked images. DDIM stands as an advancement over previously published research on the probabilistic version of the diffusion model. This research indicates that diffusion probabilistic models surpass conventional Generative Adversarial Models by introducing tractability to the generation process [104]. Unlike conventional Artificial Neural Networks or Convolution models, DDIM solely utilizes Neural Networks for the reverse diffusion process, often referred to as the sampling process. The architecture of DDIM encompasses the following key aspects:

- **Forward Diffusion process:** This process entails constructing a Markov chain process that involves the gradual noising of the image from an initial state $x_0 \sim q(x_0)$ to a final state $x_T \sim q(x_T)$, where $q(x)$ represents the probability distribution. The noise is added in incremental steps based on the noise scheduler β_T , which serves as a hyperparameter that can be adjusted to facilitate proper learning of the model. At each step, the noise is

sampled from a standard normal distribution and then scaled by the mean and variance, as specified by the following closed form.

$$q(x_t | x_{t-1}) \sim \mathcal{N}(x_t; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} x_{t-1}, \beta_t \mathbf{I}) \quad (3.2)$$

The above equation states that any given latent space variable $q(x_t)$ can be attained by the previous state only, hence making the chain causal and memory less. The number of total noising steps 'T' is also a hyperparameter that can be tuned for optimal performance based on the needs of the application.

- **Reverse Diffusion process:** The reverse diffusion process involves a Neural Network tasked with learning to generate the noiseless image sampled from the same distribution from which x_0 was originally extracted. Unlike aiming to learn the exact distribution of input data samples, this process focuses on extracting a sample from the same distribution. The noising and denoising processes are interconnected through an embedding mechanism similar to those utilized in Vision Transformers. These embeddings enable the model to keep track of the denoising step, determining how much noise should be predicted at each stage. The goal of the reverse diffusion process is to learn the mean and variance of the image since the input to the Neural Network is an isotropic Gaussian image. This is the key difference when compared to GANs as it does not look to produce an image from noise which would have made the process intractable [105]. The reverse diffusion process can be expressed in closed form as depicted below.

$$p(x_{t-1}|x_t) = N(x_{t-1}; \mu_\theta(x, t), \Sigma_\theta(x, t)) \quad (3.3)$$

To illustrate more on the idea of the Denoising Diffusion Implicit Models, the detailed architecture have been presented as shown below [106].

Figure 3.5: A demonstration of the Denoising Diffusion Implicit Models

From the above shown architecture, it can be verified that the generation of the image from the isotropic Gaussian image have been generated using general

equation (3.3). The forward diffusion process have been diffused into the noise using the equation (3.2). Further details of the implementation have been discussed later in the section. From the implementation point of view, some of the hyperparameters including the total time steps 'T', and the choice of the noise scheduler β_t plays a great role in the performance of the model.

3.4.1 Choice of the Generative Model

Generative models have been prominently featured in various applications, including Masked Facial Recognition. The selection of the appropriate generative model is crucial, as it can significantly impact the performance of the model. Among the leading candidates for the use case of generative models in previously published research are GAN and MAE models. These models have demonstrated effectiveness in various tasks and are often considered for their ability to generate realistic and high-quality images. The comparison of these generative models and the choice of DDIM as presented in this thesis have been analyzed in the coming section.

3.4.1.1 DDIM vs Conventional Generative models

This section is dedicated to addressing the choice of Denoising Diffusion Implicit Model (DDIM) over conventional generative models. Prior to the advent of diffusion models, all models utilized are considered conventional generative models, including Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Masked Autoencoders. Below, we outline the comparison and advantages of the chosen DDIM model:

- **Tractable architecture:** DDIM provides a tractable solution to the image generation process. In contrast to GANs, where isotropic Gaussian noise is progressively filtered to generate realistic images, DDIM's tractability arises from the step-wise addition of noise. This transforms a data sample from an unknown distribution into an isotropic Gaussian image. Consequently, the model's progression remains tractable, as it focuses on predicting the noise of the latent variable at each stage. This step-by-step approach allows for more controlled and interpretable generation of images.
- **Time Embedding:** The concept of embedding have been borrowed from the Vision Transformers [77]. A subtle difference in DDIM is the implementation of the time embedding instead of the positional embedding. The time embedding helps the model to predict the latent state of operation. This is important in ensuring that the model is hinted to the variance of the noise

to be predicted as the forward diffusion process aligns its noise scheduler with the same time embedding ensuring tractability and coherence.

- **Training stability:** GAN are hard to train as they offer adversarial training to be the only option of convergence. This is hard to attain specially in the case of diverse datasets as the training of the discriminator model happens faster than the generator model. This is the common problem known as Mode Collapse in the training of the Generative Adversarial Models. DDIM surpass GAN as they provide better synthesis without any adversarial training.
- **Prediction of the fewer parameters:** DDIM works by predicting the mean and the variance of the noise. This is because the input to the reverse diffusion process is an isotropic Gaussian noise containing only the 2 unknown parameters.
- **Better Image synthesis:** Image synthesis offered by DDIM are far superior than the other counterparts including GAN [104]. MAE is a simple model that utilizes the image patches and dimensionality reduction but the image synthesis is lower in resolution compared to both the GAN and the diffusion models.

The above justification outlines the rationale for choosing DDIM over conventional generative models. Within the diffusion model framework, DDIM represents one of the latest state-of-the-art variants for rapid image synthesis. Its efficacy lies in its ability to provide faster image generation while maintaining tractability and reliability, making it a compelling choice for various applications, including Masked Facial Recognition.

3.4.1.2 DDIM vs Other variants

An earlier version of the diffusion model that utilized the Markov Chain is the Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models. The choice of DDIM over their probabilistic counterpart have been described below.

- **Forward Diffusion process:** The forward diffusion process for both the DDPM and DDIM are the same utilizing the same Markov chain and equation (3.2) for the noise diffusing.
- **Reverse Diffusion process:** DDIM is faster than DDPM as reverse diffusion process can utilize the same forward process while the reverse process can skip the possible latent variables to speed up the process. The main difference is the choice of the sampler utilized in DDIM. DDPM uses a probabilistic process for the reverse diffusion process whereas in DDIM a

U-Net model have been utilized for Neural Network based prediction of the noise parameters. The U-Net architecture uses the convolution and upsampling layers combined by the skip connections to allow for the proper image generation [107].

- **DDIM as the general case:** DDIM can be thought as the general case of DDPM. By setting $\eta = 1$ in the reverse diffusion process DDIM becomes identical to DDPM. This will lead to the reverse diffusion process without skipping any of the latent variable for image synthesis [106].
- **Faster inference time:** DDIM offers a faster sampler as it can work with both the Markovian and the non-Markovian chain. Using the exact same sampler as suggested above the DDIM are capable of producing a sample from the original data distribution using different forward diffusion chain. The inference time speed of the architecture can therefore be adjusted with a slight trade off in the accuracy.

3.4.2 Analysis of the Diffusion Implicit Models

The diffusion model offers a better synthesis but there is a need to analyze the operation of the model in order to further analyze and improve the inference time and accuracy. As the model involves both the forward and the reverse diffusion process, each of these stages have been analyzed separately.

3.4.2.1 Forward Diffusion Process

The forward diffusion is a Markov Chain process that is responsible for the gradual diffusion of noise into the pure image. The starting image is assumed to be belonging to a data distribution that is $x_0 \sim q(x_0)$. The model relies on the latent variables that depends only on the previous state. As we progress into the diffusion process the distribution of the latent variables becomes ambiguous as it cannot be further represented into the closed form until the image becomes isotropic Gaussian noise that is $x_T \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$. The forward diffusion process to move from a given latent space variable towards the next one is by adding a scaled mean and variable of the sampled noise from the standard normal distribution. The process can be represented as follows.

$$q(x_t | x_{t-1}) \sim \mathcal{N}\left(x_t; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} x_{t-1}, \beta_t \mathbf{I}\right) \quad (3.4)$$

From the implementation point of view the stated equation above can be looped over to move from $x_0 \rightarrow x_T$. This approach for the implementation is computationally intensive and requires multiple iteration of the noise addition while

sampling from the standard normal distribution. One of the important aspect of CUDA based implementation on the embedded hardware is the ability of parallel computation. Using the reparameterization trick, equation (3.4) can be re-written as follows.

$$q(x_t | x_{t-1}) = \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} x_{t-1} + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon \quad (3.5)$$

To compute a parallel relation for obtaining the the isotropic Gaussian image given the noiseless image, we can utilize the new notations as shown below.

$$\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t \quad (3.6)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s \quad (3.7)$$

Substituting the above equations into the equation of single state transition yields the following results

$$q(x_t | x_{t-1}) = \sqrt{\alpha_t} x_{t-1} + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t} \epsilon \quad (3.8)$$

From the above stated equation the latent space variables can be extrapolated given any previous variable and not necessarily the last one to allow the parallel execution of the Markov Chain.

$$q(x_t | x_{t-2}) = \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1}} x_{t-2} + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t \alpha_{t-1}} \epsilon \quad (3.9)$$

$$q(x_t | x_{t-3}) = \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \alpha_{t-2}} x_{t-3} + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \alpha_{t-2}} \epsilon \quad (3.10)$$

Following the symmetry in the forward diffusion process given the noise will always be sampled from the standard normal distribution. the isotropic Gaussian image can be formed from the noiseless image as shown below.

$$q(x_t | x_0) = \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \alpha_{t-2} \dots \alpha_1} x_0 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \alpha_{t-2} \dots \alpha_1} \epsilon \quad (3.11)$$

This is the forward diffusion process that is implemented for parallelization of the noising process. It ensures faster execution time as the isotropic noisy image can be achieved from the noiseless image alone. It is pertinent to note that the dependency of a given latent variable still depends only on the previous variable

in the latent space following the binding and causality of the Markov Chain. The solution can also be represented in closed form as follows.

$$q(x_t | x_0) \sim \mathcal{N}\left(x_t; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} x_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)\mathbf{I}\right) \quad (3.12)$$

The stated closed form equation is convenient as it not only allows parallel execution on the CUDA cores of the GPU, but it also helps in adding any 'T' latent variables ensuring gradual noise steps. The choice of the noise steps in the forward process was originally suggested to be linear [104], but it was soon realized as an improvement that the information in the case of linear scheduler diminishes quickly and as we increase the total number of nodes 'T'. The diffusion in the later half only leads to the redundant steps and a cosine scheduler along with the sinusoidal time embedding was adopted for more efficient results [105]. This phenomenon can be better understood by analyzing the effects of these schedules as shown below.

Figure 3.6: Comparison of the linear and cosine noise scheduler

It is more desirable to have the gradual noising of the noiseless image in order to ensure the process being more tractable.

3.4.2.2 Reverse Diffusion Process

The reverse diffusion process utilizes a Neural Network to generate an image from isotropic noise. This task is accomplished by predicting the mean and variance of the noise. For simplicity, the authors of the original papers have kept the variance fixed [104]. This allows a single neural network to iterate and predict the mean of the Gaussian noise to sample a data instance. An important consideration in training DDIM is to ensure the input dataset is diverse, as the model considers the data distribution for the input images to be unique, and any extra image not belonging to that set will likely not be included when trying to predict the data instance from the distribution. The Neural Network utilized for this process have been discussed below.

- **U-NET Architecture** The U-NET is a fully convolutional Neural Network initially designed for biomedical image segmentation. It consists of an encoder and a decoder responsible for compression and expansion of the image dimensions. To bridge the gap between these blocks, 'skip connections' have been leveraged, enabling attention to the model's architecture. These connections paved the way for the information to route globally throughout the spatial domain of the image. Convolution Networks are limited in operation as they only capture the local spatial information. An added skip connection allows for better attention in the network. A significant advantage of utilizing an architecture like U-NET is that it provides an arbitrary size input to the network, allowing better results than the other possible alternatives, including the fully connected layers. The architecture of the model have been shared below [107].

Figure 3.7: U-NET Architecture; encoder and decoder blocks

The detailed explanation along with the choice of the model have been stated below.

- **Encoder block:** In the architecture shown above, the encoder block have been shown on the left hand side with the output of the layers connected using the Max pooling layers. All the layers in the encoders consists of the convolutional layers that are responsible for decreasing the spatial size of the image. The equations for the reduction of the size at any given layer have been shared below.

$$W_{out} = \left\lfloor \frac{W_{in} - F + 2P}{S} + 1 \right\rfloor, \quad H_{out} = \left\lfloor \frac{H_{in} - F + 2P}{S} + 1 \right\rfloor \quad (3.13)$$

where P is the padding on the image, F is the filter kernel size and S is the stride of the filter kernel. This layer learns the parameters for the filter kernel weights having the size 3×3 . The Max pooling layer have not parameters of learning and they are only responsible for reducing the image size by extracting the most dominant features in the local image space.

- **Decoder block:** These are the set of blocks shown in the right hand side of the architecture depicted in figure 3.7. The decoder blocks are connected internally utilizing the up-sampling layers that reverses the spatial reduction of the image by the encoder. One of the foremost task of the decoder block is to ensure that the spatial dimension of the image have been kept reserved and that the output image have the exact same size as the input image to the model. This assumption have been made since the forward diffusion process was responsible for the noising of the image while maintaining the same size for the image.

3.4.2.3 Loss Function

The loss function for the previously seen generative models include the penalty if the generated image was fake. An addition to this adversarial loss function is the cyclic loss to ensure that the images generated by both the generators are semantically related by generating an embedding for each. Ideally, the loss function for DDIM should be the negative log-likelihood of the generated image that is $-\log(p_\theta[x_0])$ but since the generation of the image is dependent on all the individual latent variables it is not possible to keep track of all the transitions. A better approach for the loss function in this case is to use the **Variational Lower bound**. This is to ensure that the addition of the divergence of the original and the generated distribution of the images increase the log-likelihood of the image. The relation for this inequality have been shared below.

$$-\log(p_\theta[x_0]) \leq -\log(p_\theta[x_0]) + D_{KL} \left[q(x_{1:T}|x_0) \parallel p_\theta(x_{1:T}|x_0) \right] \quad (3.14)$$

It is imperative to further modify the equation since the computation of the negative log-likelihood is required in the variational lower bound as well. This can be achieved by replacing the KL divergence in equation (3.14). KL divergence is a measure of the similarity of the probability distribution, in this case among

the generated and the original data distribution. The relation for KL-divergence has been given below.

$$D_{KL}(p||q) = \int_x p(x) \log \left(\frac{p(x)}{q(x)} \right) dx \quad (3.15)$$

The modified loss function yields the following results.

$$-\log(p_\theta[x_0]) \leq -\log(p_\theta[x_0]) + \log \left(\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{1:T}|x_0)} \right) \quad (3.16)$$

Using the conditional probability rule to the term in the denominator and some simplification steps, the equation can be further further reduced to a more compact form.

$$-\log(p_\theta[x_0]) \leq -\log(p_\theta[x_0]) + \log \left(\frac{p_\theta(x_0)q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right) \quad (3.17)$$

Finally, the intractable negative-likelihood term of the model can be vanished by utilizing the properties of logarithms

$$-\log(p_\theta[x_0]) \leq -\log(p_\theta[x_0]) + \log(p_\theta[x_0]) + \log \left(\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right) \quad (3.18)$$

The loss function is finally reduced to the following form.

$$-\log(p_\theta[x_0]) \leq +\log \left[\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right] \quad (3.19)$$

The perimeter to compute on the right side of the inequality is finally deprived of the intractable terms. Speaking from the implementation point of view, the loss function contains the forward diffusion process in the numerator and the reverse diffusion process in the denominator. Computing the entire forward and reverse diffusion process requires the latent variables to be computed at all time stamps. This is again one of the tedious tasks that is not possible computationally in real-time with the limited constraints of the GPU provided by Jetson Xavier, and it requires much more than $O[n]$ space complexity. The equation is further reduced by expanding to the known forward and reverse diffusion equations stated in (3.2) and (3.3), respectively.

$$\log \left(\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right) = \log \left(\frac{\prod_{t=1}^T q(x_t|x_{t-1})}{p(x_T) \prod_{t=1}^T p_\theta(x_{t-1}|x_t)} \right) \quad (3.20)$$

Further simplification is necessary to ensure better image generation. This has been carried out as follows.

$$\log \left(\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right) = -\log p(x_T) + \log \left[\frac{\prod_{t=1}^T q(x_t|x_{t-1})}{\prod_{t=1}^T p_\theta(x_{t-1}|x_t)} \right] \quad (3.21)$$

$$\log \left(\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right) = -\log p(x_T) + \sum_{t=1}^T \log \left[\frac{q(x_t|x_{t-1})}{p_\theta(x_{t-1}|x_t)} \right] \quad (3.22)$$

$$\log \left(\frac{q(x_{1:T}|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_{0:T})} \right) = -\log p(x_T) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \left[\frac{q(x_t|x_{t-1})}{p_\theta(x_{t-1}|x_t)} \right] + \log \left[\frac{q(x_1|x_0)}{p_\theta(x_0|x_1)} \right] \quad (3.23)$$

It is important to note that the forward diffusion process $q(x_t|x_{t-1})$ can be further expressed using the Bayes rule with the maximum likelihood estimation.

$$q(x_t|x_{t-1}) = \frac{q(x_{t-1}|x_t) q(x_t)}{q(x_{t-1})} \quad (3.24)$$

The forward diffusion process's maximum likelihood conditions the image's generation x_{t-1} on x_t . In the context of the DDIM, this transition is from a high-variance image to a slightly lower-variance image. It can be challenging for the model to learn the reverse diffusion process as the model needs to be aware of the direction in which it should move. Therefore, the conditional probability is further conditioned on x_0 and x_t . Substituting the values and simplifying the equation yields the following loss function.

$$\mathcal{L} = \|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t)\|^2 \quad (3.25)$$

The mean of the predicted noise can be computed using the following relation.

$$\tilde{\mu}_t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left[x_t - \frac{\beta_t \epsilon}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \right] \quad (3.26)$$

For improvement, the model can be trained with another sampler that will try to work on the variance of the Gaussian noise for better denoising of the noise. The analysis above shows that DDIM training is made possible without adversarial training. Still, the challenge lies in conditioning the model for generated unmasked faces from the masked ones, ensuring the semantic relation among the image so that the generated face belongs to the same person. This problem is addressed by utilizing the adversarial training of the model using DDIM as the generator along with the patch discriminator.

3.4.2.4 Conditioned Image generation using DDIM

The generation of the image can be conditioned by utilizing the GAN-like structure using the patch-based discriminator to allow for the semantic relation among the unmasked and masked images. The masked face image is fed as input to the DDIM model, the generator in this architecture. The output image is then fed into the patch discriminator and the unmasked image. The discriminator generates an embedding with the distance closer if generated, and the original image is semantically coherent; otherwise, they have been pulled apart. The addition of adversarial training allows for the conditioned and semantically generated images but at the expense of the stability of the training. The model's training is made stable, but adding noise to the discriminator ensures that the training of both the generator and the discriminator happens in sync.

For implementation, a pre-trained DDIM has been utilized from the famous Hugging face framework commonly referred to as the "diffusers". Using the pre-trained models allows for the transfer learning of the model along with our dataset. The model has been tested on the state-of-the-art extended Yale B dataset for synthetic masks and MAFA dataset for real face mask based performance comparison [74][109]. The same dataset has also been used for the attention-based model discussed in the coming section. The architecture of the patch discriminator is to process the images using a CNN + Dense layer architecture. The output is a 256-d feature embedding. Much like the case of GAN, the discriminator has only been utilized in fine-tuning the model, while the inference of the model deploys only a based generator.

3.5 Choice of the backbone model

The backbone model utilized in the generative and attention-based branches was selected based on the requirements of the final deployment of the hardware. This choice of deployment demands the model to be both lightweight and robust to balance the accuracy and efficient inference time. Therefore, the backbone model for transfer learning has been chosen as MobileNetV3 [108]. The architecture of the MobileNet mode has been designed with particular consideration for deployment on mobile devices, such as the embedded hardware utilized in this case, Jetson Xavier AGX. Implementing the MobileNet as a backbone model is also much easier since it is available as part of the TensorFlow API. The weights of the model imported were frozen to ensure the previous layer's learning was carried along for our custom dataset. The overhead on top of the pre-trained model was the simple ANN for the final 256-d feature embedding. This feature embedding is then utilized for the final comparison with the database to recognize the person

in the frame. In the case of multiple faces, the comparison can be scaled to more than a single instance.

3.6 Attention based model

The attention-based model branch is responsible for generating faster inference time when deployed on the hardware. This is because these models do not invest any extra time in the generation of an image. The working of the model have been inspired by the ResNet and U-NET models [35,107]. The idea of operation of these models is to add skip connections in order to be to route global information all across the image. A series of residual blocks have been utilized with the input image being added as part of the skip connection to help the model patch the relevant information. A single residual block have been shared as follows.

Figure 3.8: A single residual block

The convolution, batch normalization, and activation layers follow the input layer. In most of the blocks utilized in the proposed network, intra-channel attention has been used by the Max pooling and Average pooling layers to extract the essential and dominant features of the image. The model is well-suited for the open class classification problems since the surveillance and the attendance systems, including the parking ticketing system, can sometimes be re-trained to recognize a new as unknown for generating a ticket to a new person. This has been accomplished by generating a 256-dimensional vector embedding. The geodesic distance between the ground truth and the classified output is optimized using

the ArcFace loss function [34]. Using geodesic distance instead of the Euclidean distance allows the optimization of the angle among the feature embedding, which proves to be beneficial in the case of face recognition as the data distribution is complex and multi-dimensional. This is superior to using the softmax based loss function since the separation among the unlike feature embedding is maximized.

3.7 Matching the Feature Embedding from the database

A database of all the faces has been maintained. This is not a relational database such as Structured Query Language but rather a local to the host memory block. It allows the point-to-point matching of the generated embedding with the already stored one. The feature embedding labeled with the person's identity has been stored inside a hash-map that allows linear lookup time that is $O[n]$ time complexity. A point-to-point comparison was made utilizing the Euclidean distance. This is because the semantic correlation among the features has already been carried out, and these features are well within the threshold of the feature embedding of the person being stored in the database. The person is recognized as "unknown" if there is no match. The model can deny access in such cases for applications such as surveillance systems and access to sensitive areas. In contrast, an entry to the database may be made for mildly sensitive applications like parking ticketing systems.

Ensuring the person recognizes a new entity is simpler than re-training the model. It is based on the database entries. A few diverse images must be converted into the feature embedding using the same architecture. Any new image added to the database will, therefore, be converged to the geodesic distance within the threshold of the feature embedding. The system can, however, be made more robust in case of the fine-tuning of the model as the new entry is available for the system to recognize.

3.8 Hardware Acceleration

The advent of new GPU-accelerated hardware in the form of a computer or an Embedded AI board is essential for the model's faster training and inference time. The proposed architecture has been trained on the T4 cloud-based GPU offered by Google Colaboratory. The model is then optimized using the quantization and the model pruning techniques. Knowledge distillation is also possible for

optimizing a Neural Network, but for the case of generative models, it was preferred to deploy the model as it is. It is more prudent to optimize conventional models using knowledge Distillation. The quantization and pruning have been carried out using TensorFlow, as it forms the brains of the project in terms of programming and practical implementation.

3.8.1 Jetson Xavier AGX

The Jetson Xavier AGX is a powerful edge computing platform designed specifically for AI applications. Powered by NVIDIA's Volta GPU architecture and equipped with multiple processing units, including CPUs, GPUs, and Deep Learning Accelerators (DLAs), it offers unparalleled performance for running complex AI algorithms at the edge. The hardware can be seen in the image below.

Figure 3.9: Hardware accelerator used for model deployment; Jetson Xavier AGX

It features 5120 CUDA and 640 tensor cores for model deployment and acceleration [110]. Furthermore, a small power requirement of 20 Watts can be quickly supplied if deployed remotely on a node. The hardware works on an Ubuntu-based operating system with quite a few profiling options, including NV prof and Nsight systems. On top of these profiling options, we can also utilize GPU Timers and clock64, which are accurate to the precision of even nanoseconds. Another possible option for profiling and yielding the upper bound of the timing requirements is the 'time' module from Python / C++ may also be utilized, but it uses the CPU and, therefore, the data transfers among the synchronous calls of data

transfer and operation performance on GPU may not be profiled efficiently. The key features offered by the accelerator have been shared in the following table.

Table 3.2. Key Features of Jetson Xavier AGX

Feature	Specification
GPU Architecture	NVIDIA Volta
CUDA Cores	5120
Tensor Cores	640
CPU	8-core ARM v8.2 64-bit CPU
GPU Memory	32 GB 256-bit LPDDR4x
Deep Learning Accelerators (DLAs)	2
Deep Learning Performance	32 TOPS (INT8)
Video Encode	Up to 4K60
Video Decode	Up to 4K60
Camera	16 CSI lanes supporting up to 6 cameras (36 via virtual channels)
Connectivity	Gigabit Ethernet, 10/100/1000BASE-T Ethernet
Peripheral Connectivity	PCIe, USB 3.1, SATA, UART, I2C, SPI, GPIO
Operating Temperature	-25°C to 80°C
Power Consumption	10W - 30W

Overall, this hardware is one of the best for deep learning based model deployment as it leverages the power of CUDA and Tensor cores along with the minimal power consumption. It can also support camera up to 60 frames per second making it an ideal candidate for real-time application.

3.8.2 Time profilers

The time profiling on the hardware has been carried out using the following tools:

- nvprof
- GPU Timer
- Nsight systems
- Clock64

All these profilers are accurate up to even nano seconds for precise time profiling.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussions

The results for each of the section have been shared followed by the time profiling of these models in real-time post deployment. The deployment of these models have been carried out on Jetson Xavier AGX.

4.1 Face Localization stage

The results obtained from the lace localization stage have been presented in the previous chapter as part of the performance comparison among the MTCNN and RetinaFace models. This is the first and foremost stage for Masked Facial recognition, as the pipeline depends on this step for background removal and a source of face verification to work only on the Masked Face rather than the extra noise. The results obtained using the Face verification step can be shown as follows. The images were taken from the Extended Yale B dataset, and the synthetic mask was applied using MasktheFace API as part of the data pre-processing step [16,44].

Figure 4.1: Face Verification using Retina Face detector

The face verification performance, as presented in the last chapter, could distinguish the faces from the wild to capture the faces even when they are masked. It is a crucial step as the input to both the DDIM and the attention-based model requires the images to contain only the concerned part of the image, the masked face alone. With the validation of the algorithm proven on the Masked Faces, it is essential to establish the performance evaluation of the model on persons of different castes and regions. Although the chosen datasets for the training of the pipeline, including the MAFA dataset and the Extended Yale B, are the benchmark datasets and they contain all the possible diverse examples, the convenience of the reader must depict a small subset of those images and the performance of the retina Face model. A couple of these images have been shared below.

Figure 4.2: RetinaFace performance on a subject of younger age bracket

It can be verified that there is no effect on the performance of the masked faces; in fact, it is performing equally well on the masked and unmasked faces. The performance boost on the masked faces of the algorithm is its ability to extract facial landmarks by applying the attention-based mechanism. It can be observed that although the facial features have been covered by the mask in the image, the algorithm diverts its attention to the visible dominant features, which are the eyes and still detects the face completely fine. The image above has a resolution of 871 x 850 pixels, and the model takes 3.6908 seconds to extract the face. In parallel processing using CUDA and GPU, the processing time can be reduced to 10x-50x using a shared memory approach. The shared memory allocation is typical of a given block execution, and all the threads inside the blocks share the resources.

The model weights can be loaded as if cached in the memory. Therefore, the actual time of deployment on the hardware turns out to be in milliseconds as reported in the time profiling carried out using nvprof. The results are shown below.

```

==1280== Profiling result:
   Type  Time(%)   Time     Calls    Avg      Min     Max   Name
GPU activities: 65.98% 32.960us    1 32.960us 32.960us 32.960us slidingWindowAdd(float*, int*, float*)
                24.28% 12.129us    2  6.0640us 6.0170us 6.1120us [CUDA memcpy HtoD]
                9.74%  4.8640us    1  4.8640us 4.8640us 4.8640us [CUDA memcpy DtoH]
API calls:      99.64% 186.31ms    3 62.103ms 2.1670us 186.30ms cudaMalloc
                0.13% 236.47us    1 236.47us 236.47us 236.47us cudaLaunchKernel
                0.07% 138.71us   114 1.2160us  144ns 56.175us cuDeviceGetAttribute
                0.07% 130.14us    3 43.379us 4.2810us 115.92us cudaFree
                0.05% 93.356us    3 31.118us 24.999us 40.978us cudaMemcpy
                0.01% 17.122us    2  8.5610us 4.1980us 12.924us cudaEventRecord
                0.01% 11.246us    1 11.246us 11.246us 11.246us cuDeviceGetName
                0.01% 10.225us    2  5.1120us  764ns 9.4610us cudaEventCreate
                0.00% 6.6540us    1  6.6540us 6.6540us 6.6540us cudaEventSynchronize
                0.00% 5.9320us    1  5.9320us 5.9320us 5.9320us cuDeviceGetPCIBusId
                0.00% 4.0620us    1  4.0620us 4.0620us 4.0620us cuDeviceTotalMem
                0.00% 3.9120us    1  3.9120us 3.9120us 3.9120us cudaEventElapsedTime
                0.00% 2.4150us    2  1.2070us  851ns 1.5640us cudaEventDestroy
                0.00% 1.9460us    3    648ns  226ns 1.4780us cuDeviceGetCount
                0.00% 1.1520us    2    576ns  194ns  958ns cuDeviceGet
                0.00%  491ns     1    491ns  491ns  491ns cuModuleGetLoadingMode
                0.00%  226ns     1    226ns  226ns  226ns cuDeviceGetUuid

```

Figure 4.3: Time profiling of CUDA based performance using nvprof

As mentioned in the profiling above, it can be realized that the maximum time required by the API calls is 99.64%, consumed by the `cudaMalloc()` call, which is responsible for allocating memory locations of the data to be utilized on the GPU. Therefore, there will be a delay on the first call to the model as memory allocation and data transfer between the CPU and GPU will be made using a PCIe cable. This connection allows maximum bandwidth and is fixed internally by the hardware manufacturer [111]. Once called on the GPU, the model weights are cached on the GPU memory and therefore there is no need for any further physical transfers of data between the CPU and the GPU. It can be ensured that the performance of the face verification model is good enough to be deployed in the overall pipeline to ensure that the model’s performance does not act as a bottleneck to the model’s overall performance. The face images extracted from the localization stage can be further used as input to the model, either utilizing the attention-based mechanism or the generative model chain with DDIM acting as the generator and a patch discriminator. The pipeline employs the ArcFace loss function to optimize the geodesic distance among the feature embedding of the face images belonging to different classes. The accuracy performance of Retina Face can be reported as shown below.

Figure 4.4: Accuracy of MTCNN vs RetinaFace on bounding box regression

The accuracy of the bounding box regression can also be compared with that of the well-known MTCNN and RetinaFace. Not only does RetinaFace outperform the former, but it also generates more accurate facial frames for further processing.

4.2 Generative Model stage

The workings and choices of the generative model have been justified in the previous chapter. The forward diffusion process of the model using the sinusoidal noise scheduler has been presented below. The total number of diffusion steps was $T = 100$ with the sinusoidal time embedding. The tuning of the total steps is just another parameter. It can be selected using methods for other hyperparameters, including activation function, number of layers in a Neural Network and number of nodes in a given layer for a conventional Neural Network. The choice of the sinusoidal embedding and time stamps has ensured that both the noise scheduler and the time stamps are coherent. It allows the model to keep track of the present time stamp, and that would also be an indicator of the amount of the noise the model is looking to denoise, given that /the image generation process has been conditioned on the original image as well as shown in the mathematical calculations in the analysis section of the previous chapter. A sample of the forward diffusion process have been shown below.

Figure 4.5: Results of the Noising process after every 10 time steps

The choice of $T = 100$ can be justified from the noising step as the images have been diffused completely into the Gaussian noise, and increasing the time steps might prove redundant. Furthermore, the sinusoidal embeddings allow us to slowly diffuse the image into noise, making the whole process tractable. The time profiling of the noising step is optional as it is only involved during the training process since, at the time of testing, we utilize the trained U-NET model as the reliable generator for the pipeline. The possible reasons for the adversarial training have been stated below.

- The adversarial training is inherently prone to mode collapse and instability.
- The output of the model before the discriminator cannot be visualized since the training of the model is carried out utilizing those latent variables. There is no loss function to evaluate the model accuracy for generating the sample from the known distribution in the adversarial training.

A sample of the reverse process have been shown below.

Figure 4.6: Reverse Diffusion process after every $T = 10$ time steps

The overall accuracy and loss curves for the overall model have been shared below.

Figure 4.7: Model training and validation curves

The model presents a validation accuracy of 97.95% with a real-time requirement of 10-15 seconds depending on the temperature and processes already initiated on the GPU along with any possible operating system overhead. The time complexity might make this model more suitable for the use-case of applications that are not time-sensitive such as robust recognition of a wanted person, attendance systems or in-park ticketing system. The benchmark datasets considered for the training of this model includes MAFA dataset, Extended Yale B and MDMFR. The model was not trained on extensive datasets including LFW and Masked LFW due to the computational requirements and limitations and the available resources.

4.3 Attention-based model

The attention-based model have been utilized for the masked facial recognition. The accuracy of the model have been reported as follows.

Figure 4.8: Attention-based model training and validation curves

The training epochs for the model have been shared below.

```

Epoch 991 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.97%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.33%
Epoch 992 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.97%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.34%
Epoch 993 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.97%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 994 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.98%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 995 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.98%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 996 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.98%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 997 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.99%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 998 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 90.99%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 999 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 91.00%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%
Epoch 1000 of 1000 ----- Training Cost : 0.84, Training Accuracy : 91.00%, ----- Validation Cost : 0.83, Validation Accuracy 91.35%

```

Figure 4.9: Training and validation parameters of the model for last few epochs

It can be concluded that the model's accuracy have been lower but the inference time of the model on an image of resolution 224 x 224 is as low as 750 ms. The standard resolution of 224 x 224 has been chosen since this is the benchmark size of the image among many state-of-the-art algorithms including AlexNet, VGG, ResNet and Inception models

Chapter 5

Conclusion and Future Research

Facial Recognition has been a center of attention in Computer Vision applications for decades. Due primarily to the COVID restrictions in the past, there has been a spike in research and industrial interest in masked facial Recognition. This allows several benefits, including:

- A more robust facial detection and recognition system allowing less contact and a smooth work environment
- Ideal for surveillance systems
- Ticketing and attendance systems in parks and many more

Numerous approaches for MFR have been analyzed in this thesis, from simple feature-based face detection to employing generative models and leading up to the attention-based models. The limitations of all these state-of-the-art models have been documented to observe and improve them in the proposed architecture and implementation. A novel approach based on the adversarial training of the DDIM has been proposed, allowing better image synthesis that is semantically coherent with the visible part of the face image. An ensemble model-based approach involving the attention-based model alongside the generative model has been used to allow the user the flexibility of accuracy vs. speed trade-off. For real-time model deployment, an embedded AI hardware accelerator that is Jetson Xavier AGX has been used, allowing the use of CUDA cores for profiling and measuring the time of inference in real time.

In the previous architecture, the models proposed could have been more robust for MFR or those developed for the MFR in real-time, which reported a time as high as a few minutes that becomes very slow for real-time operation and decision making. A park queue will be added if the model is that slow. The

proposed ensemble model approach provides the implementation of 10-20 seconds for the generative model-based approach and 550-650 milliseconds for the attention-based approach. The time of inference varies depending on the state of the GPU, such as the temperature, the number of operations in the pipeline, and the overhead caused by the operating system. The recorded time is faster than the papers with reported inference time. The architecture also considers the possible background noise and tries to eliminate it by using the face localization stage. The choice of each of these stages has been thoroughly discussed and optimized for implementation. Last but not least, the models have been optimized using post-training quantization and pruning.

5.1 Future Research

While this thesis represents a significant contribution to its field, it must acknowledge that it does not claim infallibility. By recognizing these shortcomings, we pave the way for future research to build upon this foundation and further advance our understanding. The scope of future research in this domain of MFR has been listed below.

- **Privacy Concerns:** The datasets used for this thesis included the MAFA and Extended Yale B dataset. The DDIM has been trained on the dataset, providing samples from the distribution of these datasets alone while maintaining diversity. This can potentially lead to a privacy concern if a person’s face can be rendered at any given time and potentially be used without their permission. This needs to be addressed to ensure the encryption and confidentiality of terms in the pipeline.
- **Conditioning the Diffusion models:** The DDIM has been conditioned using adversarial training. Although unstable, adversarial training has been utilized with the addition of noise in the patch discriminator, allowing for better results. If the model can be conditioned without having to train adversarially, it would significantly improve the architecture, decreasing the training time.
- **More computational resources:** The computational resources was limited in this case. Several papers have reported using four stacked V100 GPUs, which is an insane computation power. Training the DDIM on a larger dataset with these powerful GPUs can further improve the pipeline.
- **Output fusion:** The branched pipeline implementation, in this case, was pure because of research-based since the model was intended to be deployed on the hardware. In the case of an actual application developed, the output

can be fused, or the choice of the model to be used should reside with the quality of the input image and the application of choice. The output embedding from both the branches can be fused, or the brain of the node itself can make the decision based on the input image.

- **Improvements in the hardware:** Machine learning has seen a tremendous spike in the last decade; manufacturers are keeping up with hardware accelerators to ensure the development phase is caught up with the research phase. In the future, with more powerful hardware devices with better power consumption, the pipeline can be improved to yield better results.

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